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**Lie Symmetry Theory-Based Approaches for the Computation of Mode
Shapes of Vibrating Structures**

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Abstract

Vibrations of elastic bodies play a crucial role in the dynamic analysis of structures. For that, displacement patterns of vibrating systems, i.e., mode shapes, have shown great importance for assessing their motion behavior, whose modeling usually arises from differential equations. The Lie symmetry method deals with groups of transformations that systematically expose potential simplifications for differential equations such as order reductions, domain compression, and linearizations, providing the straightforward construction of closed-form solutions. This qualification exam report addresses a study on mode shapes of rods, Euler-Bernoulli, and Timoshenko beams via Lie symmetries. Reductions of order and new spaces of variables are accomplished for the mode shape equations of these models, yielding well-posed boundary value problems. In particular, the mode shape model for longitudinal vibration of rods with varying cross-section areas turns into Riccati equations and quadratures. Exact numerically stable mode shape expressions of uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams, subject to classical and non-classical boundary conditions, are proposed through the Lie symmetry method for accurately assessing high-frequency solutions. Two successive order reductions for the mode shape equations of uniform Timoshenko beams are computed, converting the second-order ordinary differential equations into first-order equivalent ones.

Keywords: Mode shapes. Lie symmetries. Order reductions. Rods. Euler-Bernoulli beams. Timoshenko beams. Numerically stable exact solutions.

Resumo

A análise vibratória de corpos elásticos compõe um dos pilares da dinâmica de estruturas. Nesse contexto, modos de vibrar expressam padrões de deslocamento e são efetivos para a caracterização do comportamento vibratório de estruturas, cujos modelos geralmente são descritos por equações diferenciais. O método das simetrias de Lie permite definir grupos de transformações para equações diferenciais de forma que reduções de ordem, domínios compactos, linearizações e soluções analíticas fechadas sejam obtidos. Este relatório, referente ao exame geral de qualificação, aborda um estudo sobre modos de vibrar longitudinais de barras e transversais vigas de Euler-Bernoulli e Timoshenko através do método das simetrias de Lie. Desse modo, obtêm-se novos espaços de variáveis e reduções de ordem para as equações dos modos de vibrar dos modelos referidos, resultando, de forma geral, em equações diferenciais de menor complexidade e em problemas de valor de contorno bem condicionados. Em particular, equações de Riccati e quadraturas resultam do processo de redução de ordem para a equação dos modos de vibrar de barras com seção não-uniforme. Propõem-se soluções numericamente estáveis para os modos de vibrar de vigas uniformes de Euler-Bernoulli, sujeitas a diversas condições de contorno clássicas e não-clássicas, através de novos espaços de variáveis via simetrias de Lie, onde se têm soluções exatas e acuradas para altas frequências. Além disso, reduções de ordem sucessivas são determinadas para as equações diferenciais ordinárias dos modos de vibrar de vigas de Timoshenko, obtendo, assim, duas equações correspondentes de primeira ordem.

Palavras-chave: Modos de vibrar. Simetrias de Lie. Reduções de ordem. Barras. Vigas de Euler-Bernoulli. Vigas de Timoshenko. Soluções exatas numericamente estáveis.

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List of Acronyms

BC	Boundary condition
BVP	Boundary value problem
DE	Differential equation
IBVP	Initial and boundary value problem
ODE	Ordinary differential equation
PDE	Partial differential equation

List of Symbols

i, j, k	Indexes
x	Independent variable / spatial coordinate
z_j	Dependent variable
$z_j^{(k)}$	k th derivative of z_j with respect to its argument
\mathbf{z}	Set of dependent variables
$\mathbf{z}^{\{k\}}$	Set of all k th-order derivatives of the \mathbf{z} components
G	Group
g_1, g_2, g_3	Group elements
e	Identity element
\mathcal{L}	Lie algebra
\mathcal{L}^i	i th Lie subalgebra
X, Z_j	Analytic functions
n_d	Number of dependent variables

n_i	Number of independent variables
\bar{x}	Independent variable subject to a infinitesimal transformation
\bar{z}_j	Dependent variable subject to a infinitesimal transformation
$\bar{\mathbf{z}}$	Set of dependent variables subject to a infinitesimal transformation
$\bar{z}_j^{(k)}$	k th-extended dependent variable
$\bar{\mathbf{z}}^{\{k\}}$	Set of all k th-extended \mathbf{z} components
\mathcal{O}	High-order term
${}_{(\sigma)}\mathcal{F}_n$	σ th-order ordinary differential equation
${}_{(\sigma)}\bar{\mathcal{F}}_n$	σ th-order ordinary differential equation subject to a infinitesimal transformation
\mathcal{D}	Total derivative operator
f_j	Analytic functions
r, v_j	Invariants
\mathbf{v}	Set of invariants
$v_j^{(k)}$	k th-order differential invariant
$\mathbf{v}^{\{k\}}$	Set of k th-order differential invariants
$\overset{i}{r}, \overset{i}{v}_j$	Invariants associated to the i th reduction
$\overset{i}{\mathbf{v}}$	Set of invariants associated to the i th reduction
$\overset{i}{v}_j^{(k)}$	k th-order differential invariant associated to the i th reduction
$\overset{i}{\mathbf{v}}^{\{k\}}$	Set of k th-order differential invariants associated to the i th reduction
R, V_j	Canonical coordinates
W	Projection
s_i	i th boundary surface
\mathcal{S}	Number of boundary surfaces
\mathcal{B}_c	Boundary condition
\tilde{u}, \tilde{w}	Vibration displacement solutions
E	Young's modulus
G	Shear modulus
S	Cross-sectional area function

I	Cross-sectional area moment of inertia
l_i	End of the vibrating structure
t	Time
u, w	Mode shape displacement functions
λ	Wavenumber
b_i	Constant value from the left-right convention sign at the boundary l_i
\mathcal{V}_i	Constant quantity from the shearing boundary restrictions at l_i
\mathcal{M}_i	Constant quantity from the bending moment boundary restrictions at l_i
$K_{i,T}$	Translational spring stiffness at l_i
$K_{i,R}$	Rotational spring stiffness at l_i
j	Imaginary unit
m_i	Attached mass at l_i
J_i	Rotational inertia at l_i
$\mathcal{C}_1, \mathcal{C}_2, \mathcal{C}_3, \mathcal{C}_4,$ $\mathcal{A}_1, \mathcal{A}_2, \mathcal{A}_3, \mathcal{A}_4$	Constants of integration
a_1, a_2, a_3	Cross-sectional area parameters of rods
y	Spatial coordinate
D	Flexural stiffness of plates
h	Thickness

Greek Letters

μ	Dummy index
Φ	Law of composition
δ_1, δ_2	Real constants
ϵ	Continuous Lie group parameter
\mathcal{X}	Infinitesimal generator

\mathcal{X}_p	Infinitesimal generator with the label p
${}_{(k)}\mathcal{X}$	k th-order prolonged infinitesimal generator
ξ, η_j	Infinitesimal functions associated to \mathcal{X}
${}_{(k)}\eta_j$	k th-order prolonged infinitesimal function η_j
$\xi^{(p)}, \eta_{j^{(p)}}$	Infinitesimal functions associated to \mathcal{X}_p
${}_{(k)}\eta_{j^{(p)}}$	k th-order prolonged infinitesimal function $\eta_{j^{(p)}}$
σ	Order of the highest derivative of an ordinary differential equation
ϑ_j, θ_j	Auxiliary invariant functions
ρ	Density
ω	Natural angular frequency
$\tilde{\phi}$	Cross-sectional rotation solution
ϕ	Mode shape rotation function
β, γ	Parameters of the Timoshenko beam model
$\tilde{\lambda}_1, \tilde{\lambda}_2, \tilde{\lambda}_3$	Generalized wavenumbers
κ	Shear factor
Θ_1, Θ_2	Analytic functions
α_0	Real constant
$\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4$	Transformation parameters
ψ^i	Invariant associated to the i th reduction
$\psi^i{}^{(k)}$	k th-order differential invariant associated to the i th reduction
ν	Poisson's ratio

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1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter outlines the subject of this qualification exam report. First, Section 1.1 presents the motivation for carrying out this research. Sections 1.2 and 1.3 address the objectives and accomplished contributions of this work, respectively. Finally, Section 1.4 indicates the organization of this report's chapters.

1.1 MOTIVATION

Vibration problems arise in many fields of engineering and science (BASNER *et al.*, 2014; PREUMONT, 2011; IBRAHIM, 2008; HASHEMI; GOLNARAGHI; PATLA, 2004; GRIFFIN; ERDREICH, 1991). The modeling of real vibrating structures is usually embodied by differential equations (DEs) within this framework. Hence, several methods for solving DEs have been applied to study structures' behavior (BOYCE; DIPRIMA; MEADE, 2018; ZILL, 2013; LEE, 2009). Meanwhile, the level of feasibility of a model can certainly be reduced if complicated DEs are associated with them, essentially due to difficulty for solving the related equations, which may represent a challenge to accurately grasp the system's dynamics (CAO *et al.*, 2012; HONG *et al.*, 2011; HE; FU, 2001). In this sense, robust mathematical tools play an important role in the study of vibration problems.

The Lie symmetry method is a mathematical theory aimed to systematically reveal symmetries of DEs (DRESNER, 1998; BLUMAN; KUMEI, 1989; OLVER, 1986). These symmetries expose information about potential transformations that retain equations' solutions invariant and allow straightforward constructions of exact solutions by employing analytical simplifications techniques, e.g., order reductions, linearizations, and domain compressions, based on conservation principles of the analyzed systems (CHERNIHA; DAVYDOVYCH, 2020; BASQUEROTTO *et al.*, 2019; CHERNIHA; KOVALENKO, 2012; MENINI; TORNAMBÈ, 2009). Besides these benefits, Lie's method contributions are barely observed in engineering problems (OLIVERI, 2004; KASTRUP, 1983).

The investigation of Lie symmetries of physical systems has revealed interesting features about their properties (ZHI, 2021; BOCHAROV, 1999). Vibration problems have already been evaluated under the symmetry view (TIAN, 2020; AHMED; ZAMAN; SALEH,

2017; DJONDJOROV, 1995). Conversely, the analysis of mode shape equations, which provide how the vibrating structure behaves spatially, is seldom observed in literature through the Lie symmetry method. The combination of complex solution engineering problems, such as assessing mode shapes of structures with varying cross-sections, and the math tools provided by the Lie symmetry method can yield original and efficient resolution methods (SADAT *et al.*, 2020; ALI; MAHOMED; QADIR, 2009). This suggests the possibility of studying a wide variety of vibrating problems under the symmetry view and enhancing the Lie symmetry utilization in engineering problems.

Concerning mode shape equations of vibrating structures, Lie symmetries may either aid the construction of exact closed-form solutions or enhance the efficiency of numerical methods for computing approximate solutions (NUNES; SILVA; MENCNIK, 2019; JAMAL; JOHNPIILLAI, 2019). Once the Lie symmetry method establishes transformations of coordinates that allow writing DEs in new spaces of variables, unique characteristics of these spaces may help with the resolution procedure, for instance, enabling to deal with lower-order equations and/or avoiding numerical issues when considering numerical methods for DEs¹ (ZHANG; LI, 2020; YANG; HUA, 2014). Regarding mode shapes of vibrating structures with varying cross-sections, symbolic approaches for exact computing solutions are not often observed mainly due to the complexity of the associated DEs (LI, 2000; LEE; KUO, 1992).

Analytical expressions for mode shape functions of relevant models of uniform rods and beams, e.g., Euler-Bernoulli and Timoshenko beams, are available in the literature for several combinations of boundary conditions (BCs) (BISHOP; JOHNSON, 2011; HAN; BENAROYA; WEI, 1999; GROVER, 1972) and high-frequency analysis has been proven essential these vibration problems (ZHANG; LIN, 2019; SHIN *et al.*, 2018; MOTAMED; RUNBORG, 2015; NOVAK; HONZIK; BRUNEAU, 2017; WARBURTON, 1954). However, when it comes to the high-frequency analysis of vibration modes, the numerical assessment of exact mode shape expressions is usually prone to numerical instabilities, i.e., by plotting the mode shapes against the position along with the vibrating structure. This happens due to round-off errors from operations between closely similar hyperbolic terms, in which exponential growth follows the frequency increasing. One strategy for avoiding the aforementioned numerical issues consists in rewriting mode shape solutions with the aid of mathematical identities until they stop exhibiting round-off errors (KHA-SAWNEH; SEGALMAN, 2019; GONÇALVES *et al.*, 2019; GONÇALVES; PELOW;

¹One interesting topic in this area consist in the study of Lie symmetries and mapping of boundary value problems (BVPs) into more convenient domains (SESHADRI; NA, 1985).

BRENNAN, 2018; GONÇALVES; BRENNAN; ELLIOTT, 2007). On the other hand, the Lie symmetry method can provide naturally well-posed BVPs with the assistance of new spaces of variables, where there are no concerns about the fitting of mode shapes expressions from low to high frequencies.

Within this work's scope, this report aims to provide a study on mode shape functions of vibrating structures via the Lie symmetry method and, concomitantly, broaden the application of Lie symmetries in engineering problems, fostering their usage for solving problems in this field. So far, mode shapes of longitudinally vibrating rods and transversely vibrating Euler-Bernoulli and Timoshenko beams have been studied via the Lie symmetry method. The Lie theory is introduced in a straightforward way for systems of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) as well as order reduction procedures based on symmetry methods.

1.2 OBJECTIVE

This work intends to provide a Lie symmetry analysis of mode shape equations of vibration problems such as rods and beams, focusing on the computation of order reductions and analytical solutions for them.

1.3 MAIN CONTRIBUTIONS

The contributions of the present report rely on:

- presenting a review of the Lie symmetry method for systems of ODEs in a concise way and without requiring a profound theoretical background on the field;
- deriving a reduced-order equation and closed-form solutions for mode shapes of longitudinally vibrating rods with varying cross-sections;
- providing numerically stable mode shapes functions for uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams undergoing transverse vibration and subject to classical and non-classical BCs;
- computing reduced-order mode shape equations of Timoshenko beams via successive Lie symmetry transformations by the differential invariant method.

1.4 OUTLINE

This work is organized into five chapters as follows:

- **Chapter 1 - Introduction** addresses the motivation, objectives, and contributions of this work.
- **Chapter 2 - Lie Symmetries** comprises a literature review, the required theoretical background on Lie groups, and the mathematical formulation of the Lie symmetry method. Essential symmetry concepts and techniques for order reductions of ODEs are also covered.
- **Chapter 3 - Vibration of Rods and Beams** provides the vibration theory for rods and beams as well as remarks about their mode shape solutions.
- **Chapter 4 - Results and Discussion** presents the results of this work, comprising closed-form solutions for vibrating rods, Euler-Bernoulli and Timoshenko beams through reduced-order DEs via the Lie symmetry method.
- **Chapter 5 - Final Remarks** discusses the conclusions of this report and suggests the next steps for the research.
- **Appendix I** complements Chapter 4 with the computation of frequency equations of uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams for additional combinations of BCs.

2 LIE SYMMETRIES

This chapter introduces the Lie symmetry method for DEs. First, Section 2.1 presents an overview of Sophus Lie's contributions and several documented applications of symmetry methods in the literature. Section 2.2 describes the used notation along the text. Then, Section 2.3 gives basic concepts for understanding Lie groups, required for developing the algorithm of Section 2.4 for computing Lie point symmetries of systems of ODEs. Section 2.5 brings the order reduction method via differential invariants and Section 2.6 defines the computation procedure for canonical coordinates associated to symmetry transformations. Section 2.7 discusses the invariance formulation for BVPs and Section 2.8 finally outlines this chapter's remarks.

2.1 LITERATURE REVIEW

Symmetry brings back to nature, order, and harmony (LEDERMAN, 2004; WEYL, 1952). From the electronic orbitals of a simple atom to several ruling principles of the universe, symmetry shapes physical phenomena and support unveiling them. Within this framework, symmetries are intrinsically connected to laws of conservation and the concept of invariance (FEYNMAN, 1963). In modern mathematics, the notion of symmetry arose from the brilliant scientist Sophus Lie in the 19th century, later connected to physics laws by Emmy Noether through the insightful Noether's Theorem (NOETHER, 1918; LIE, 1888; LIE, 1880). Other prominent authors in the symmetry area that deserve to be mentioned are G. Scheffers, F. Engel, and W. Killing for their noteworthy contributions (LIE; SCHEFFERS, 1891; LIE; ENGEL, 1890; KILLING, 1890; KILLING, 1888). On top of that, the study of symmetries had a substantial impact on remarkable research fields such as the theory of relativity (EINSTEIN, 2015).

Inspired by Abel's and Galois' research about group theory applications in algebraic equations, Sophus Lie endeavored to accomplish a similar theory for DEs (BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002; YAGLOM, 1988). Lie found during his research that several integration techniques for solving DEs are systematically based on invariance principles. From this perspective, the derivation of solutions for DEs via analytical procedures does not depend on lucky guesses and can be methodically defined for different classes of equations (OLIV-

ERI, 2010). The concept of invariance refers to the unchanged “appearance” of an object² after a transformation, and the more symmetric is the object, the more modifications can be done, keeping it invariant (CANTWELL, 2002; OLVER, 1999). Right now, one can take examples of possible transformations from simple translations and rotations, related to the conservation of linear and angular momentum for mechanical systems, respectively, to Galilean and Lorentz transformations, which play essential roles in classical and modern physics (see (BOCHAROV, 1999) for more examples of transformations) (ROCHA; RIZZUTI; MOTA, 2013; LEDERMAN, 2004; MARSDEN; RATIU, 1999).

The Lie symmetry method consists of a theory devoted to compute groups of transformations for DEs so that it enables the construction of exact solutions for these equations through analytical simplifications, order reductions, and linearization techniques when dealing with nonlinear equations (BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002; OLVER, 1986). In this context, symmetry can be defined as a transformation that maps solutions of DEs, either ordinary equations or partial ones, to other solutions based on invariance principles. For ODEs, every symmetry implies a potential reduction of order for the equation (in the case of systems of ODEs, each symmetry yields a reduction of order for a single equation of the system). In contrast, for partial differential equations (PDEs), the reduction procedure provides equations with fewer independent variables, eventually transformed into ODEs (GOVINDER, 2001; ZHDANOV; TSYFRA; POPOVYCH, 1999; OVSIANNIKOV, 1982).

Although Lie’s ideas were groundbreaking and well-founded for solving DEs by the time they were proposed, when it lacked convenient methods for unifying their resolution procedures, symmetry methods remained relatively unapplied until the last decades, just after computer algebra started gaining prominence (BAUMANN, 2000; HEREMAN, 1994). Symmetry methods are highly algorithmic and, sometimes, deal with the solution of a considerable number of PDEs; therefore, one may expect fruitful results when associating them to computer algebra (WINTERNITZ, 2003). Recently, several new applications of symmetries have been found in fields such as pure and applied mathematics, e.g., algebra, geometry, topology, and probability, natural sciences as well as in engineering problems, for instance in solid and fluid mechanics, heat transfer, control theory, and machine learning (OLVER, 1986; CHEN *et al.*, 2021; HRDINA; NÁVRAT; ZALABOVÁ, 2021).

In physics, the applicability of Lie symmetries is mainly noticed in analytical mechanics (CORDANI, 2013; LUO, 2009; MILLER, 1980; BOGOYAVLENSKIJ, 1997), modern physics (BATLLE *et al.*, 2019; NASCHIE, 2008), optics (ZHI, 2021) and astrophysics

²This notion works for physical objects as well as for mathematical objects such as DEs.

(ABEBE; MAHARAJ, 2019; FROLOV; KRTOUŠ; KUBIZŇÁK, 2017), in addition to the insightful interpretations of classical and quantum problems that it provides (FEYNMAN, 1963). Similarly, Lie symmetries have been used in the biological field for solving interesting models in epidemiology (NUCCI, 2005), population (ZHANG; LI, 2020; GRUBER; LENCZEWSKI, 1986) and tumor growing (CHERNIHA; DAVYDOVYCH, 2020), along with chemistry problems (SÁEZ, 2020; SÁEZ *et al.*, 2020; GARRIDO *et al.*, 2018). The symmetry approach is also concerned with numerical methods, especially when the computation of analytical solutions is intractable or for cases in which the only measurement of performance for the numerical method is associated with invariant quantities under symmetry transformations (KUMAR *et al.*, 2018; VANEEVA *et al.*, 2014).

Regarding engineering problems, the Lie symmetries have been giving significant contributions for studying dynamics of mechanical systems (BASQUEROTTO; RUIZ, 2020; BASQUEROTTO; RIGHETTO; SILVA, 2018), fluid dynamics (REHMAN; MALIK, 2019; GAI; LI; SUDAO, 2020; SHE; CHEN; HUSSAIN, 2017; RAZAFINDRALANDY; HAMDOUNI; SAYED, 2012; YÜRÜSOY; PAKDEMIRLI, 1997) as well as vibrating problems (ZHANG, 2019; AHMED; ZAMAN; SALEH, 2017; FRANCO, 2015). In particular for vibrating structures, the authors Liu and Li (2009) provided the laws of conservation and exact solutions for two high-order rod equations by reducing the related PDEs to corresponding ODEs via the Lie symmetry method; meanwhile, Vassilev (1997) computed the laws of conservation for nonlinear elastic rods using the Lie symmetries of the associated differential equations of the model with the aid of the Noether's theorem.

When it comes to beams, the complete Lie symmetry classification of the static Euler-Bernoulli beam equation was brought by Bokhari, Mahomed and Zaman (2010) and, then, Ruiz, Muriel and Ramírez (2019) provided convenient exact solutions and first integrals for the equation as mentioned earlier, which is not trivial once it has a nonsolvable Lie algebra. For vibrating cases, Huang, Li and Yu (2017) presented the computation of symmetries and the Lie group classification for a generalized nonlinear beam model, carrying out reductions of order after taking known values to the beam's parameters, and Vassilev and Djondjorov (2003) determined the admitted symmetry generators and conservation laws for vibrating Euler-Bernoulli beams and Poisson–Kirchhoff type plates through the analysis of their PDEs. Bokhari, Mahomed and Zaman (2012) computed and classified the admitted Lie symmetry group for vibrating Euler-Bernoulli beams and derived the exact solution for a severe case of an initial and boundary value problem (IBVP), according to the admitted boundaries by the symmetry transformation.

PDEs of Timoshenko beams have already been considered under the Lie symmetry

view. For instance, Al-Omari, Zaman and Azad (2017) obtained the optimal system of subalgebras and its related invariant quantities, including the explicit solution for a specific BVP of a vibrating Timoshenko beam. Jamal and Johnpillai (2019) derived exact solutions for the vibrating Timoshenko thermoelastic beam model with the support of Lie symmetries, computing similarity solutions for the problem. Moreover, vibrating beams and plates on elastic foundations were investigated by the authors Bocko, Nohajová and Harčarik (2012) and Bocko, Glodová and Lengvarský (2014).

2.2 NOTATION

Lie symmetries are the object of study of many books and researches in literature, which address the Lie symmetry method approximately in the same way (CANTWELL, 2002; BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002; OLVER, 1986; OVSIANNIKOV, 1982). However, there is no standard notation regarding derivatives, superscripts, and subscripts. This section provides a reasonable description of the notation used in this report.

Consider (\cdot) as a general dependent variable of a single argument. Following Lagrange's notation for derivatives, $(\cdot)^{(k)}$ denotes the k th derivative of the dependent variable with respect to its argument. For instance, let $z_j = z_j(x)$ whose derivative of order k is given by:

$$z_j^{(k)} = \frac{d^k z_j}{dx^k}.$$

Bold variables represent sets of variables whose components are denoted by non-bold terms with a subscript, e.g., $\mathbf{z} = (z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n)$ is a n -dimensional set lying on \mathbb{R}^n . Equally important, $(\cdot)^{\{k\}}$ gives the set of the k th-order derivatives of all components whenever (\cdot) is a set of variables, in this case $\mathbf{z}^{\{k\}} = (z_1^{(k)}, z_2^{(k)}, \dots, z_n^{(k)})$.

In order to differ from the notation of set components, terms with left subscripts such as ${}_{(k)}(\cdot)$ stand for k th-order prolongations of Lie theory elements, i.e., infinitesimal generators and infinitesimal functions. Furthermore, the upper index at $\binom{k}{\cdot}$ is used for variables and sets when dealing with successive reductions of order for avoiding the need of choosing new names for variables at each step of reduction for the corresponding DEs.

The summation convention by Einstein notation has been used to concisely describe all variables, derivatives, and infinitesimal functions in expressions along with this chapter. The Greek letter μ is consistently utilized through this report as a dummy index to symbolize summations in expressions such as (HARRISON; JOSEPH, 2016; EINSTEIN,

1916):

$$a_\mu z_\mu = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i z_i,$$

where μ has to appear twice in a single term in order to be admitted as the so-called dummy index. In this example, the range of the summation index terms is represented by $\mu = 1, 2, \dots, n$, from the lower to the upper bounds of the summation.

At last, all functions and variables are firstly introduced specifying their dependencies and then written in the short form for the sake of conciseness (when there is no possible ambiguity), e.g., an infinitesimal function is first noted as $\xi(x, \mathbf{z})$ and thereafter just ξ .

2.3 BACKGROUND IN SYMMETRY GROUPS AND LIE ALGEBRAS

Let G be a non-empty set of elements³ with a law of composition (operator) Φ between its elements. Then, G is called a group if it satisfies the following axioms $\forall g_1, g_2, g_3 \in G$ (LIPSCHUTZ, 2018; BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002):

1. $\Phi(g_1, g_2)$ is an element of G (closure property).
2. $\Phi(g_1, \Phi(g_2, g_3)) = \Phi(\Phi(g_1, g_2), g_3)$ (associative property).
3. There is an element $e \in G$ for every g_1 for which $\Phi(g_1, e) = g_1$ (identity element).
4. There exists the inverse g_1^{-1} for each g_1 such that $\Phi(g_1, g_1^{-1}) = e$ (inverse element).

Similarly, a subgroup of G is a subset of its elements with the same law of composition between them (BLUMAN; KUMEI, 1989).

A Lie algebra \mathcal{L} is a vector space with a bilinear operation⁴ which admits an operation of commutation between two infinitesimal generators. Let the basis⁵ $\mathcal{X}_{p_1}, \mathcal{X}_{p_2}, \mathcal{X}_{p_3} \in \mathcal{L}$ be infinitesimal generators of a group of transformations (Lie group), the commutator operation between them is defined as follows (OLVER, 1986; OVSIANNIKOV, 1982):

$$[\mathcal{X}_{p_1}, \mathcal{X}_{p_2}] = \mathcal{X}_{p_1} \mathcal{X}_{p_2} - \mathcal{X}_{p_2} \mathcal{X}_{p_1}.$$

satisfying the following axioms for $\delta_1, \delta_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ (GILMORE, 2006; HUMPHREYS, 1972):

³Examples of group elements: integers, vectors, matrices, transformations, etc. (SESHADRI; NA, 1985).

⁴A bilinear operation is a rule which associates any pair of group components to a unique element of the same group (SAMUEL, 1975).

⁵A basis comprises the set with the highest number of linearly independent vectors (GILMORE, 2006).

1. $[\mathcal{X}_{p_1}, \mathcal{X}_{p_2}] = -[\mathcal{X}_{p_2}, \mathcal{X}_{p_1}]$ (skew-symmetry property).
2. $[\delta_1 \mathcal{X}_{p_1} + \delta_2 \mathcal{X}_{p_2}, \mathcal{X}_{p_3}] = \delta_1 [\mathcal{X}_{p_1}, \mathcal{X}_{p_3}] + \delta_2 [\mathcal{X}_{p_2}, \mathcal{X}_{p_3}]$ (multiplication associative property).
3. $[\mathcal{X}_{p_1}, [\mathcal{X}_{p_2}, \mathcal{X}_{p_3}]] + [\mathcal{X}_{p_2}, [\mathcal{X}_{p_3}, \mathcal{X}_{p_1}]] + [\mathcal{X}_{p_3}, [\mathcal{X}_{p_1}, \mathcal{X}_{p_2}]] = 0$ (Jacobi's identity).

In particular, two infinitesimal generators commute when $[\mathcal{X}_{p_1}, \mathcal{X}_{p_2}] = 0$, and, in the case of $\mathcal{X}_{p_1}, \mathcal{X}_{p_2} \in \mathcal{L}$ for all p_1, p_2 admitted infinitesimal generators, it gives an Abelian Lie algebra⁶ (or an Abelian subalgebra if \mathcal{X}_{p_1} and \mathcal{X}_{p_2} are elements of a subalgebra).

Lie algebras are elementary formed by subalgebras. Consider a Lie algebra \mathcal{L} and a subalgebra $\mathcal{L}^i \subset \mathcal{L}$, then \mathcal{L}^i is called ideal if the commutator $[\mathcal{X}_{p_1}, \mathcal{X}_{p_2}] \in \mathcal{L}^i$ for any $\mathcal{X}_{p_1} \in \mathcal{L}$ and $\mathcal{X}_{p_2} \in \mathcal{L}^i$. This means that one can set the chain of subalgebras (BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002; HYDON, 1998):

$$\mathcal{L}^0 \subset \mathcal{L}^1 \subset \dots \subset \mathcal{L}^q = \mathcal{L}, \quad (1)$$

which configures a q -dimensional solvable Lie algebra. Note that \mathcal{L}^0 is always admitted as an ideal subalgebra.

In general, groups of transformation are divided into two categories: discrete and continuous groups. The former is commonly associated with procedures for enhancing the computational efficiency of numerical methods (BIBI; FEROUZE, 2020; YANG *et al.*, 2012), specifying a finite number of possible transformations. In the latter, continuous groups of transformation represent a broader class of transformations in which Lie symmetry methods are highly efficient (CANTWELL, 2002; BLUMAN; KUMEI, 1989). The thing is, no straightforward method for completely computing sets of discrete symmetries was known until the recent contributions of the authors Reid, Weih and Wittkopf (1993) and Hydon (1998), which makes the field of discrete symmetries of DEs relatively unexplored.

The number of admitted parameters by continuous groups is crucial for their characterization (ANCO; GANDARIAS, 2020; SAKKARAVARTHI *et al.*, 2018; YANG; HUA, 2014; KAC *et al.*, 2018). Continuous groups that only depend on one parameter are called one-parameter Lie groups and the ones which admit more than that are the so-called multiparameter Lie groups. Each parameter leads to a transformation and, hence, to an infinitesimal generator. Roughly speaking, a multiparameter Lie group of q parameters, i.e., a q -parameter group, reduces to q distinct independent infinitesimal generators; therefore, the theory for one-parameter Lie groups can be considered for the study of multi-

⁶A Lie group is Abelian if $\Phi(g_1, g_2) = \Phi(g_2, g_1)$; accordingly, an Abelian Lie algebra follows from the condition $[\mathcal{X}_{p_1}, \mathcal{X}_{p_2}] = [\mathcal{X}_{p_2}, \mathcal{X}_{p_1}] = 0$ (BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002; OVSIANNIKOV, 1982).

parameter groups (BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002; OLVER, 1986). In this sense, one-parameter Lie groups are introduced for systems of ODEs in the following.

2.4 ONE-PARAMETER LIE GROUPS FOR SYSTEMS OF ORDINARY DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

One-parameter Lie groups of transformations, or shortly one-parameter Lie groups, consist in sets of continuous transformations which satisfies the axioms (1-4) of a group and depend on a continuous parameter $\epsilon \in \mathbb{R}$ (MOTSEPA, 2016). Let $X(x, \mathbf{z}, \epsilon)$ and $Z_j(x, \mathbf{z}, \epsilon)$ be infinitely differentiable functions acting on the space of variables (x, \mathbf{z}) that represent the point transformations⁷ (BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002; DRESNER, 1998):

$$\bar{x} = X(x, \mathbf{z}, \epsilon), \quad \bar{z}_j = Z_j(x, \mathbf{z}, \epsilon) \quad (j = 1, 2, \dots, n_d), \quad (2)$$

mapping the source space through a rule (transformation) that associates all its elements to the target space of variables $(\bar{x}, \bar{\mathbf{z}})$ (SAMUEL, 1975). These point transformations are admitted a system of n_d ODEs as follows:

$$\mathcal{F}_n(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \mathbf{z}^{\{\sigma\}}) = 0 \quad (n = 1, 2, \dots, n_d), \quad (3)$$

where x is the independent variable, $\mathbf{z} = (z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{n_d})$ represents the dependent variables and σ is highest derivative order in the system.

The expansion by the Taylor series of the set of transformations of Eq. (2) around $\epsilon = 0$ gives (BOCKO; NOHAJOVÁ; HARČARIK, 2012; CANTWELL, 2002; HYDON, 1998):

$$\bar{x} = x + \epsilon \left(\frac{\partial X}{\partial \epsilon} \right) \Big|_{\epsilon=0} + \frac{\epsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 X}{\partial \epsilon^2} \right) \Big|_{\epsilon=0} + \dots = x + \epsilon \left(\frac{\partial X}{\partial \epsilon} \right) \Big|_{\epsilon=0} + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2), \quad (4)$$

and

$$\bar{z}_j = z_j + \epsilon \left(\frac{\partial Z_j}{\partial \epsilon} \right) \Big|_{\epsilon=0} + \frac{\epsilon^2}{2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 Z_j}{\partial \epsilon^2} \right) \Big|_{\epsilon=0} + \dots = z_j + \epsilon \left(\frac{\partial Z_j}{\partial \epsilon} \right) \Big|_{\epsilon=0} + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2)$ comprises terms of order higher than one. Subsequently, one can introduce the infinitesimal functions:

$$\xi(x, \mathbf{z}) \equiv \left(\frac{\partial X}{\partial \epsilon} \right) \Big|_{\epsilon=0}, \quad \eta_j(x, \mathbf{z}) \equiv \left(\frac{\partial Z_j}{\partial \epsilon} \right) \Big|_{\epsilon=0} \quad (j = 1, 2, \dots, n_d), \quad (6)$$

⁷A point transformations means a mapping which only depend on the dependent and independent variables of the problem (OLIVERI, 2010).

and neglecting high-order terms ($\epsilon^2 \approx 0$ due to the expansion about $\epsilon = 0$) in Eqs. (4) and (5), the infinitesimal transformations for the space of variables (x, \mathbf{z}) simply follows (BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002; COHEN, 1911):

$$\bar{x} = x + \epsilon \xi(x, \mathbf{z}), \quad \bar{z}_j = z_j + \epsilon \eta_j(x, \mathbf{z}), \quad (7)$$

mapping each point (x, \mathbf{z}) into $(\bar{x}, \bar{\mathbf{z}})$ for $\bar{\mathbf{z}} = (\bar{z}_1, \bar{z}_2, \dots, \bar{z}_{n_d})$.

The connection between Lie groups and infinitesimal transformations is formally established by the First Fundamental Theorem of Lie with an one-to-one correspondence, i.e., each one-parameter Lie group associates to a single infinitesimal transformation. This theorem states that the corresponding Lie group is obtained from the given infinitesimal transformations by solving Eq. (6) subject to the initial conditions (MOTSEPA, 2016; COHEN, 1911):

$$\bar{x}|_{\epsilon=0} = x, \quad \bar{z}_j|_{\epsilon=0} = z_j \quad (j = 1, 2, \dots, n_d). \quad (8)$$

Infinitesimal transformations can be naturally extended to act on the complete space of variables of Eq. (3), that is, $(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \mathbf{z}^{\{\sigma\}})$ -space (*jet space*). These extensions produce the so-called prolonged infinitesimal functions and the procedure for computing them is described in the following.

2.4.1 Extended infinitesimal transformations

From the group theory perspective, derivatives of dependent variables can be considered as simply coordinates by the introduction of *jet spaces* (CANTWELL, 2002; OLVER, 1986). Let the $(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}})$ -space holds first-extended transformations such as (BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002; COHEN, 1911):

$$\bar{z}_j^{(1)} = \frac{\mathcal{D}\{z_j + \epsilon \eta_j\}}{\mathcal{D}\{x + \epsilon \xi\}} = \frac{z_j^{(1)} + \epsilon \mathcal{D}\{\eta_j\}}{1 + \epsilon \mathcal{D}\{\xi\}} \quad (j = 1, 2, \dots, n_d), \quad (9)$$

where \mathcal{D} is the total derivative operator:

$$\mathcal{D} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + z_\mu^{(1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial z_\mu} + \dots + z_\mu^{(\sigma)} \frac{\partial}{\partial z_\mu^{(\sigma-1)}}, \quad (10)$$

for the dummy index $\mu = 1, 2, \dots, n_d$.

Considering the Binomial Rule⁸ at the denominator of Eq. (9) with $\epsilon^2 \approx 0$, one can

⁸ $(1+a)^b = 1 + ab + \frac{a^2b}{2!}(b-1) + \dots$ (HALL; KNIGHT, 1957).

rearrange first-extended transformations as follows (BOCKO; NOHAJOVÁ; HARČARIK, 2012; BLUMAN; COLE, 1974):

$$\bar{z}_j^{(1)} \approx \left(z_j^{(1)} + \epsilon \mathcal{D}\{\eta_j\} \right) (1 - \epsilon \mathcal{D}\{\xi\}) = z_j^{(1)} + \epsilon \left(\mathcal{D}\{\eta_j\} - z_j^{(1)} \mathcal{D}\{\xi\} \right), \quad (11)$$

from where the first prolonged infinitesimal function for z_j is:

$${}_{(1)}\eta_j = \mathcal{D}\{\eta_j\} - z_j^{(1)} \mathcal{D}\{\xi\}. \quad (12)$$

Similarly, k th-extended transformations are given as follows:

$$\bar{z}_j^{(k)} \approx z_j^{(k)} + \epsilon \left[{}_{(k)}\eta_j(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \mathbf{z}^{\{k\}}) \right] \quad (k \geq 2), \quad (13)$$

with the k th-prolonged infinitesimal function:

$${}_{(k)}\eta_j = \mathcal{D}\left\{{}_{(k-1)}\eta_j\right\} - z_j^{(k)} \mathcal{D}\{\xi\} \quad (k \geq 2), \quad (14)$$

comprising, in addition to Eqs. (11) and (12), all derivatives of the *jet* space of Eq. (3) for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n_d$ and $k = 1, 2, \dots, \sigma$.

2.4.2 Infinitesimal generators

Infinitesimal generators are tangent vectors to their space of variable, therefore defined as follows (OLIVERI, 2010; OVSIANNIKOV, 1982):

$$\mathcal{X} = \xi \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \eta_\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial z_\mu}, \quad (15)$$

acting on the non-prolonged space of variables, i.e., (x, \mathbf{z}) -space, for $\mu = 1, 2, \dots, n_d$. In the same way that infinitesimal transformations naturally prolongs to extended ones, a k th-order prolonged infinitesimal generator acting on the $(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \mathbf{z}^{\{k\}})$ -space of variables can be written in the form:

$${}_{(k)}\mathcal{X} = \mathcal{X} + {}_{(1)}\eta_\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial z_\mu^{(1)}} + \dots + {}_{(k)}\eta_\mu \frac{\partial}{\partial z_\mu^{(k)}} \quad (\mu = 1, 2, \dots, n_d, \quad k \geq 1). \quad (16)$$

2.4.3 Infinitesimal criterion for invariance

Let ${}_{(\sigma)}\mathcal{X}$ be an admitted (prolonged) infinitesimal generator of Eq. (3). The expansion by the Taylor series of the aforementioned systems of ODEs gives (CANTWELL, 2002):

$$\bar{\mathcal{F}}_n = \mathcal{F}_n + \epsilon {}_{(\sigma)}\mathcal{X}\{\mathcal{F}_n\} + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^2) \quad (n = 1, 2, \dots, n_d), \quad (17)$$

where $\bar{\mathcal{F}}_n = \bar{\mathcal{F}}_n(\bar{x}, \bar{z}, \bar{z}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \bar{z}^{\{\sigma\}})$ corresponds to the set DEs after the transformation by the admitted Lie group. The concept of invariance requires that $\bar{\mathcal{F}}_n = \mathcal{F}_n$, from this and with $\epsilon^2 \approx 0$ it follows that (BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002; OLVER, 1986):

$${}_{(\sigma)}\mathcal{X}\{\mathcal{F}_n\} = 0, \quad \text{when } \mathcal{F}_n(x, z, z^{\{1\}}, \dots, z^{\{\sigma\}}) = 0 \quad (n = 1, 2, \dots, n_d). \quad (18)$$

This relation's validity stands for the condition of having an invariant object, in this case a system of ODEs, under a given symmetry group represented by the vector field ${}_{(\sigma)}\mathcal{X}$. Eq. (18) gives the infinitesimal criterion for invariance of DEs, whose resolution provides the admitted Lie group. At this point, all prolonged infinitesimal functions must be written in terms of the non-prolonged ξ and η_j functions. The introduction of $z_j^{(\sigma)} = f_j(x, z, z^{\{1\}}, \dots, z^{\{\sigma-1\}})$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n_d$ from Eq. (3) in Eq. (18) allows some derivative terms to be removed and, by equating the coefficients of the remaining derivatives of z to zeros in the resulting equation, it yields a system of linear PDEs known as determining equations (OLIVERI, 2010; OVSIANNIKOV, 1982).

The integration of the determining equations gives the expressions of the infinitesimal functions in terms of x and z and, hence, the admitted point transformations from the Lie group. Computer algebra associated with several symbolic manipulation packages plays an essential role for solving determining equations, especially when dealing with high order DEs (VU; JEFFERSON; CARMINATI, 2012; DIMAS; TSOUBELIS, 2005; BUTCHER; CARMINATI; VU, 2003; BAUMANN, 2000; HEREMAN, 1994).

2.5 DIFFERENTIAL INVARIANTS

Two methods are usually applied to achieve reductions of order of DEs via Lie symmetries: the Canonical Coordinates Method and the Differential Invariant Method. In general, the latter is more beneficial for equations that admit multiparameter Lie groups with a solvable algebra. Thus successive reductions can be performed without computing intermediate reduced equations (AL-KINDI; ZIAD, 2019; BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002; BLUMAN; KUMEI, 1989). In this sense, this section aims to describe the Differential Invariant Method for successive reductions of order for systems of ODEs.

A differential invariant consists of a function that is invariant under an infinitesimal transformation (OLVER, 1999; OLVER, 1995). As mentioned earlier, if a system of ODEs admits a one-parameter Lie group, the associated transformation reduces the order of a single equation of the system. For systems of first-order ODEs, the same transformation

gives a reduction in the number of equations of the system by one (HYDON, 1998; OLVER, 1986). Otherwise, multiple reductions can be achieved if a multiparameter⁹ Lie group is admitted by the system. In this case, one may promote the reductions in such a way that each reduced equation possesses the most significant amount of remaining symmetries in order to ensure subsequent reductions, i.e., the order reduction process has to obey the solvability chain array from Eq. (1). This means that a reduced-order equation inherits the remaining non-used symmetries from the corresponding higher-order ones (CANTWELL, 2002; GOVINDER, 2001).

If a system of ODEs in the form of Eq. (3) admits at least an one-parameter Lie group of transformations represented by the symmetry generator \mathcal{X} , one can set the invariants $r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{v}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \mathbf{v}^{\{\sigma\}}$ from the relations (BLUMAN, 1990):

$$\mathcal{X}\{r(x, \mathbf{z})\} = 0, \quad (1)\mathcal{X}\{\mathbf{v}(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}})\} = 0, \quad (19)$$

and

$${}^{(k)}\mathcal{X}\{\mathbf{v}^{\{k-1\}}(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \mathbf{z}^{\{k\}})\} = 0 \quad (k = 2, 3, \dots, \sigma+1), \quad (20)$$

where $\mathbf{v} = (v_1, v_2, \dots, v_{n_d})$.

These invariance relations can be explicitly written as PDEs. For instance, the differential invariant $v_1^{(\sigma-1)}$ follows from:

$${}^{(\sigma)}\mathcal{X}\{v_1^{(\sigma-1)}\} = \xi \frac{\partial v_1^{(\sigma-1)}}{\partial x} + \eta_\mu \frac{\partial v_1^{(\sigma-1)}}{\partial z_\mu} + {}^{(1)}\eta_\mu \frac{\partial v_1^{(\sigma-1)}}{\partial z_\mu^{(1)}} + \dots + {}^{(\sigma)}\eta_\mu \frac{\partial v_1^{(\sigma-1)}}{\partial z_\mu^{(\sigma)}} = 0, \quad (21)$$

for $\mu = 1, 2, \dots, n_d$, whose linearly independent solutions, i.e., the differential invariants, are found as the constants of integration of the characteristic equation¹⁰ (OLIVERI, 2010; BLUMAN; COLE, 1974):

$$\frac{dx}{\xi} = \frac{dz_j}{\eta_j} = \frac{dz_j^{(1)}}{{}^{(1)}\eta_j} = \dots = \frac{dz_j^{(\sigma)}}{{}^{(\sigma)}\eta_j} \quad (j = 1, 2, \dots, n_d). \quad (22)$$

The first ODE from Eq. (22) can be rearranged as (HYDON, 1998; COHEN, 1911):

$$\frac{dz_j}{dx} = \frac{\eta_j}{\xi}, \quad (23)$$

which holds the general solution $r(x, \mathbf{z}) = \mathcal{C}_1$ for any j , where \mathcal{C}_1 is a constant of integra-

⁹Multiparameter Lie groups hold simultaneously more than one linearly independent infinitesimal transformations (COHEN, 1911).

¹⁰The characteristic equation of an infinitesimal transformation relates the infinitesimal functions definition, from where $d\epsilon = \frac{dx}{\xi} = \frac{dz_j}{\eta_j}$, as well as its prolongations (BLUMAN; COLE, 1974).

tion. At this point, the expressions of ξ and η_j are already known from the resolution of the determining equations, thus the computation of the aforementioned invariant simply follows from the integration of Eq. (23) over x .

Recalling first-prolonged infinitesimal functions from Eq. (12), the first differential invariant follows from:

$$\frac{dz_j^{(1)}}{dx} = \frac{{}_{(1)}\eta_j}{\xi}, \quad (24)$$

where, for computing its solution, it is necessary to previously remove the dependence on z_j . This can be done by introducing $z_j = \vartheta_j(x, r)$ in the right-hand side of Eq. (24) whenever it occurs (note that both ξ and ${}_{(1)}\eta_j$ are functions of z_j) (BLUMAN; COLE, 1974). Similarly to the procedure for the previous invariant, the integration of Eq. (24) gives $v_j(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}}) = \mathcal{C}_{2(j)}$, where $\mathcal{C}_{2(j)}$ is invariant under ${}_{(1)}\mathcal{X}$, for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n_d$.

For the next differential invariants $v_j^{(1)}$, the two already found invariants can be applied to eliminate variables in such a way to simplify the computation procedure. Accordingly, if one choose the relation $\frac{dz_j^{(2)}}{dx} = \frac{d{}_{(2)}\eta_j}{d\xi}$, z_j and $z_j^{(1)}$ dependencies must be removed from it by taking the auxiliary functions $z_j = \vartheta_j(x, r)$ and $z_j^{(1)} = \theta_j(x, r, \mathbf{v})$, which resolution leads to $v_j^{(1)}(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}}, \mathbf{z}^{\{2\}}) = \mathcal{C}_{3(j)}$. Otherwise, as a second option, the relation $\frac{dz_j^{(2)}}{dz_j} = \frac{d{}_{(2)}\eta_j}{d\eta_j}$ can be used to compute the aforementioned invariant, requiring the removal of the dependencies of x and $z_j^{(1)}$ from this equation, similarly to the last case, or x and z_j from $\frac{dz_j^{(2)}}{dz_j^{(1)}} = \frac{d{}_{(2)}\eta_j}{d{}_{(1)}\eta_j}$. Here, it can be chosen the simplest of these three case for computing second differential invariants (BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002; COHEN, 1911).

Differential invariants of order higher than two can be obtained by constructing analogous relations to second-order invariants, i.e., picking out the corresponding equation from Eq. (22) and eliminating the non-related dependencies. Then, Eq. (3) can be expressed in the new space of variables by the computed invariants, leading to a reduced equation:

$${}_{(\sigma-1)}\mathcal{F}_1(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{v}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \mathbf{v}^{\{\sigma-1\}}) = 0, \quad (25)$$

and the remaining non-reduced ones as follows:

$${}_{(\sigma)}\mathcal{F}_n(r, \mathbf{v}, \mathbf{v}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \mathbf{v}^{\{\sigma\}}) = 0 \quad (n = 2, \dots, n_d). \quad (26)$$

For DEs which admit only a one-parameter Lie group, the reduction procedure for Lie point symmetries is done. However, if it admits a q -dimensional solvable Lie algebra, the system of ODEs can be reduced by q . In some cases, this can be associated with

the integration of ODEs by quadratures¹¹ (BASARAB-HORWATH, 1991; GONZÁLEZ-LÓPEZ, 1988). The procedure for successive reductions is presented in the following.

2.5.1 Successive reductions of order under a solvable Lie algebra

The solvability chain rules the preferential ordering for using the infinitesimal generators as far as successive order reductions are concerned. If two infinitesimal generators possess the commutative relation $[\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_2] = \lambda \mathcal{X}_1$ for $\lambda \neq 0$, the first reduction should be performed using \mathcal{X}_1 in order not to lose additional symmetries from the full group. Otherwise, if $\lambda = 0$, there is no preferential ordering for that (BLUMAN, 1990; OLVER, 1986). The subsequent procedure for successive order reductions is based on the works of Bluman (1990) and Hydon (1998).

Consider a solvable Lie algebra formed by the infinitesimal generators $\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_2, \dots, \mathcal{X}_q$ admitted by the Eq. (3) and written in the form:

$$\mathcal{X}_p = \xi_{(p)}(x, \mathbf{z}) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \eta_{\mu(p)}(x, \mathbf{z}) \frac{\partial}{\partial z_\mu} \quad (p = 1, 2, \dots, q, \quad \mu = 1, 2, \dots, n_d). \quad (27)$$

where the subscripts between parenthesis for the infinitesimal functions refer to their corresponding label p of the infinitesimal generator.

The invariance formulation for the first reduction of order using \mathcal{X}_1 holds:

$$\mathcal{X}_1 \left\{ \overset{1}{r}(x, \mathbf{z}) \right\} = 0, \quad (1)\mathcal{X}_1 \left\{ \overset{1}{v}_j(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}}) \right\} = 0, \quad (28)$$

and

$$({}^k)\mathcal{X}_1 \left\{ \overset{1(k-1)}{v}_j(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \mathbf{z}^{\{k\}}) \right\} = 0 \quad (k = 2, \dots, \sigma + 1), \quad (29)$$

which gives the set of invariants $\left(\overset{1}{r}, \overset{1}{\mathbf{v}}, \overset{1\{1\}}{\mathbf{v}}, \dots, \overset{1\{\sigma\}}{\mathbf{v}} \right)$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n_d$, i.e., the constants of integration from a characteristic equation similar to Eq. (22).

The next step consists in mapping the subsequent symmetry generator \mathcal{X}_2 (from the solvable algebra) to the new space of variables, described by the differential invariants from the first step. Accordingly, their associated infinitesimal functions are given through the relations:

$$\xi_{(2)} \left(\overset{1}{r}, \overset{1}{\mathbf{v}} \right) = \mathcal{X}_2 \left\{ \overset{1}{r} \right\}, \quad \eta_{j(2)} \left(\overset{1}{r}, \overset{1}{\mathbf{v}} \right) = (1)\mathcal{X}_2 \left\{ \overset{1}{v}_j \right\}, \quad (30)$$

¹¹The integration by quadratures suggests solving the differential equation in terms of known analytic functions (ABRAMOWITZ; STEGUN; ROMER, 1988).

and for the first prolonged infinitesimal function:

$${}_{(1)}\eta_{j(2)}\left(\overset{1}{r}, \overset{1}{\mathbf{v}}, \overset{1}{\mathbf{v}}^{\{1\}}\right) = {}_{(2)}\mathcal{X}_2\left\{\overset{1}{v}_j^{(1)}\right\}, \quad (31)$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n_d$. From this it follows that the infinitesimal generator is written as:

$$\mathcal{X}_2 = \xi_{(2)}\frac{\partial}{\partial \overset{1}{r}} + \eta_{\mu(2)}\frac{\partial}{\partial \overset{1}{v}_\mu}, \quad (32)$$

and its first extension simply follows:

$${}_{(1)}\mathcal{X}_2 = \mathcal{X}_2 + {}_{(1)}\eta_{\mu(2)}\frac{\partial}{\partial \overset{1}{v}_\mu}, \quad (33)$$

where $\mu = 1, 2, \dots, n_d$.

Note that the non-prolonged infinitesimal generator from Eq. (32) acts on the $(\overset{1}{r}, \overset{1}{\mathbf{v}})$ -space, corresponding to the $(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}})$ -space for the original variables. Once \mathcal{X}_2 remains admitted by the system of ODEs after the first reduction, the invariance formulation holds:

$${}_{(1)}\mathcal{X}_2\left\{\overset{2}{r}(\overset{1}{r}, \overset{1}{\mathbf{v}})\right\} = 0, \quad {}_{(2)}\mathcal{X}_2\left\{\overset{2}{v}_j\left(\overset{1}{r}, \overset{1}{\mathbf{v}}, \overset{1}{\mathbf{v}}^{\{1\}}\right)\right\} = 0, \quad (34)$$

and

$${}_{(k)}\mathcal{X}_2\left\{\overset{2}{v}_j^{(k-2)}\left(\overset{1}{r}, \overset{1}{\mathbf{v}}, \overset{1}{\mathbf{v}}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \overset{1}{\mathbf{v}}^{\{k-1\}}\right)\right\} = 0 \quad (k = 3, \dots, \sigma+1). \quad (35)$$

Then, infinitesimal functions from the third transformation in the chain (i.e., \mathcal{X}_3) can be written for as follows:

$$\xi_{(3)}\left(\overset{2}{r}, \overset{2}{\mathbf{v}}\right) = {}_{(1)}\mathcal{X}_3\left\{\overset{2}{r}\right\}, \quad \eta_{j(3)}\left(\overset{2}{r}, \overset{2}{\mathbf{v}}\right) = {}_{(2)}\mathcal{X}_3\left\{\overset{2}{v}_j\right\}, \quad (36)$$

and the first prolonged infinitesimal function being:

$${}_{(1)}\eta_{j(3)}\left(\overset{2}{r}, \overset{2}{\mathbf{v}}, \overset{2}{\mathbf{v}}^{\{1\}}\right) = {}_{(3)}\mathcal{X}_3\left\{\overset{2}{v}_j^{(1)}\right\}. \quad (37)$$

for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n_d$.

The infinitesimal generator \mathcal{X}_3 is in this reduced space of variables:

$$\mathcal{X}_3 = \xi_{(3)}\frac{\partial}{\partial \overset{2}{r}} + \eta_{\mu(3)}\frac{\partial}{\partial \overset{2}{v}_\mu}, \quad (38)$$

whose first prolongation is given by:

$$({}_1)\mathcal{X}_3 = \mathcal{X}_3 + ({}_1)\eta_{\mu(3)} \frac{\partial}{\partial v_{\mu}^2(1)}, \quad (39)$$

for the whole space, where $\mu = 1, 2, \dots, n_d$.

Upcoming reductions are performed following the continuation of the algorithm presented for two successive reductions of order. The invariance relations for the i th reduction of order for a system of ODEs which admits a q -dimensional solvable Lie algebra ($q > 2$) are written as:

$$({}_{i-1})\mathcal{X}_i \left\{ \overset{i}{r} \left(\overset{i-1}{r}, \overset{i-1}{\mathbf{v}} \right) \right\} = 0, \quad ({}_i)\mathcal{X}_i \left\{ \overset{i}{v}_j \left(\overset{i-1}{r}, \overset{i-1}{\mathbf{v}}, \overset{i-1}{\mathbf{v}}^{\{1\}} \right) \right\} = 0, \quad (40)$$

and

$$({}_k)\mathcal{X}_i \left\{ \overset{i}{v}_j \left(\overset{i-1}{r}, \overset{i-1}{\mathbf{v}}, \overset{i-1}{\mathbf{v}}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \overset{i-1}{\mathbf{v}}^{\{k-i+1\}} \right) \right\} = 0 \quad (k = 1+i, 2+i, \dots, \sigma+1), \quad (41)$$

recalling that ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n_d$). When $i = 1$ (first reduction), the infinitesimal generator is $({}_0)\mathcal{X}_1 = \mathcal{X}_1$ and the space of variables $\left(\overset{0}{r}, \overset{0}{\mathbf{v}}, \overset{0}{\mathbf{v}}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \overset{0}{\mathbf{v}}^{\{\sigma-1\}} \right)$ shall be equivalent to $(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \mathbf{z}^{\{\sigma\}})$.

Then, the mapped infinitesimal functions for the i th reduction are:

$$\xi_{(i+1)} \left(\overset{i}{r}, \overset{i}{\mathbf{v}} \right) = ({}_{i-1})\mathcal{X}_{i+1} \left\{ \overset{i}{r} \right\}, \quad \eta_{j(i+1)} \left(\overset{i}{r}, \overset{i}{\mathbf{v}} \right) = ({}_i)\mathcal{X}_{i+1} \left\{ \overset{i}{v}_j \right\}, \quad (42)$$

and prolonged infinitesimal functions follows from:

$$({}_k)\eta_{j(i+1)} \left(\overset{i}{r}, \overset{i}{\mathbf{v}}, \overset{i}{\mathbf{v}}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \overset{i}{\mathbf{v}}^{\{k\}} \right) = ({}_{i+k})\mathcal{X}_{i+1} \left\{ \overset{i}{v}_j \right\} \quad (k = 1, 2, \dots, \sigma - i), \quad (43)$$

The next infinitesimal generator written in the new space of variables, i.e., spawned by the invariants from the i th reduction, is:

$$\mathcal{X}_{i+1} = \xi_{(i+1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \overset{i}{r}} + \eta_{\mu(i+1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \overset{i}{v}_{\mu}}, \quad (44)$$

whose k th-order prolongation is given by:

$$({}_k)\mathcal{X}_{i+1} = \mathcal{X}_{i+1} + ({}_1)\eta_{\mu(i+1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \overset{i}{v}_{\mu}^2(1)} + \dots + ({}_k)\eta_{\mu(i+1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial \overset{i}{v}_{\mu}^k} \quad (\mu = 1, 2, \dots, n_d, 1 \leq k \leq \sigma - i). \quad (45)$$

For succeeding reductions, the infinitesimal generator from Eq. (44) and its prolonga-

tions replace the equivalent ones in Eq. (40) and Eq. (41) for the next stage i of reduction ($i = 1, 2, \dots, q$). Finally, the system of ODEs can be replaced by an equivalent one reduced q times, in which the last computed invariants are the dependent and independent variables.

2.6 CANONICAL COORDINATES

Canonical coordinates are sets of variables in which Lie groups are expressed by groups of translations. This property represents the possibility of integrating the ODEs directly (HYDON, 1998). Let R and $V_j(R)$ be canonical coordinates for a transformation led by the infinitesimal functions ξ and η_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, n_d$). Once these coordinates relate to groups of translation, they can be computed by the resolution of the following system (CANTWELL, 2002; BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002):

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{X}\{R\} &= \xi \frac{\partial R}{\partial x} + \eta_\mu \frac{\partial R}{\partial z_\mu} = 0, \\ \mathcal{X}\{V_n\} &= \xi \frac{\partial V_n}{\partial x} + \eta_\mu \frac{\partial V_n}{\partial z_\mu} = 0 \quad (n = 1, 2, \dots, n_d - 1),\end{aligned}\tag{46}$$

and

$$\mathcal{X}\{V_{n_d}\} = \xi \frac{\partial V_{n_d}}{\partial x} + \eta_\mu \frac{\partial V_{n_d}}{\partial z_\mu} = 1,\tag{47}$$

for $\mu = 1, 2, \dots, n_d$. The general procedure for solving this system of equations consists in assembling a characteristic equation such as Eq. (22). Here, just the non-prolonged quantities are needed once the demanding derivatives for the *jet* space can be accomplished by deriving V_j with respect to R . Notice that $n_d = 1$ in the case of single ODEs, thus only Eq. (47) is taken into consideration for the dependent variable $V = V_{n_d}$.

For systems or single first-order ODEs, a change of variables to canonical coordinates leads to integration via quadrature. Besides that, these coordinates can also be useful to reduce the order of ODEs when associated to projections such as $W = \frac{dV}{dR}$, once equations transcribed by canonical coordinates does not depend explicitly on V (BASQUEROTTO; RIGHETTO; SILVA, 2018; RUIZ; MURIEL, 2017; OLIVERI, 2010).

2.7 INVARIANCE FORMULATION FOR BOUNDARY VALUE PROBLEMS

Exact solutions for BVPs can be found through the Lie symmetry method by seeking a subgroup of the full Lie group admitted both by the ODE or systems of ODEs and the BCs of the problem. The procedure for finding the subgroups mentioned above consists of applying the invariance formulation to the boundaries and discard those transformations from the Lie group that do not keep the boundaries invariant (SESHADRI; NA, 1985). Hence, besides the reduction of order of the DE, e.g., via the Differential Invariant Method, the BVP can be mapped to a reduced-order one (BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002).

After computing the full Lie group admitted by system of ODEs (or single ODEs), the invariance condition can be applied to a BVP with \mathcal{S} boundary surfaces $s_i(x)$ as follows (GAI; LI; SUDAO, 2020; CHERNIHA; KOVALENKO, 2012):

$$\mathcal{X}\{s_i(x)\} = 0 \quad \text{when } s_i = 0 \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{S}), \quad (48)$$

for all its BCs, denoted by \mathcal{B}_c :

$${}_{(k)}\mathcal{X}\{\mathcal{B}_c(x, \mathbf{z}, \mathbf{z}^{\{1\}}, \dots, \mathbf{z}^{\{k\}})\} = 0 \quad \text{when } \mathcal{B}_c|_{s_i=0} = 0 \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, \mathcal{S}). \quad (49)$$

Here, the non-prolonged symmetry generator ${}_{(0)}\mathcal{X} = \mathcal{X}$ has to be considered for zero-order BCs, namely $\mathcal{B}_c(x, \mathbf{z}) = 0$.

2.8 PARTIAL REMARKS

The first part of this chapter provided general concepts about symmetries and invariance, followed by Sophus Lie's contributions to group theory for DEs. Then, a brief review of applications of symmetry methods was presented for science and engineering problems, focusing on vibrating problems that are similar to this work's scope.

To begin with the Lie symmetry method description, the standard notation and the required theoretical background on symmetry groups and Lie algebras were provided. The introduction of one-parameter Lie groups and the procedure for computing Lie symmetries were given for systems of ODEs. The differential invariant method and canonical coordinates for symmetry transformations were presented, and the algorithm for successive order reductions under solvable algebras was given. Finally, this chapter presented the invariance formulation for BVPs.

3 VIBRATION OF RODS AND BEAMS

Vibration analysis of continuous elastic structures can be carried out using several analytical theories, whose choice primarily relies on the level of complexity of the geometrical and material properties of the structure as well as the level of accuracy sought when computing the related displacement solutions (DOYLE, 1989; RAYLEIGH, 1945). Among these theories, one can mention the classical theories for vibrating rods, Euler-Bernoulli, and Timoshenko beams, which address a broad class of mechanical problems (ZHANG; THOMPSON; SHENG, 2020; BANERJEE, 2020; NACHUM; ALTUS, 2007; YOON; SON; AHN, 2007). The modeling of these distributed-parameter structures considers homogeneous, isotropic, and linearly-elastic materials, according to Hooke's law, fitting for small deformations (WEAVER; TIMOSHENKO; YOUNG, 1990). This chapter contains a discussion about the aforementioned vibrating models, studied in this report under the Lie symmetries view.

3.1 LONGITUDINAL VIBRATION OF RODS

The classical theory for the longitudinal vibration of rods, also known as bars, considers the fundamental hypothesis that all the cross-sections of the rod remain plane and only move in its axial direction while compressing or extending. Here, the neglected lateral displacement does not produce significant accuracy errors for thin rods, in which the cross-sectional's dimensions is considerably smaller than the wavelength of vibration (WEAVER; TIMOSHENKO; YOUNG, 1990; GROVER, 1972). The motion equation for longitudinal vibrating free rods with non-uniform areas is given as follows (INMAN, 2013; KINSLER *et al.*, 1999):

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(ES \frac{\partial \tilde{u}}{\partial x} \right) - \rho S \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{u}}{\partial t^2} = 0, \quad x \in]l_1, l_2[, \quad t > 0, \quad (50)$$

where E is the Young's modulus, S is the cross-sectional area function and ρ is the density of the rod. Furthermore, $\tilde{u} = \tilde{u}(x, t)$ is the rod's longitudinal displacement, $x \in [l_1; l_2]$ represents the position along the rod and $t \geq 0$ denotes time.

Consider an hamonic non-trivial solution of Eq. (50) such as $\tilde{u} = u e^{i\omega t}$, where $u = u(x)$ and ω are the mode shape functions and the natural angular frequencies of the rod,

respectively. From this, for all above-mentioned parameters admitted as constant except for the cross-sectional function $S = S(x)$, the motion equation becomes:

$$u^{(2)} + \frac{S^{(1)}}{S}u^{(1)} + \lambda^2 u = 0, \quad (51)$$

which gives the mode shape equation for non-uniform rods with varying cross-sectional areas, where $\lambda = (\rho/E)^{\frac{1}{2}} \omega$ is the wavenumber¹².

Solutions for the longitudinal displacement of vibrating rods can be constructed through the superposition of several mode shape functions in addition to the admitted harmonic solution and the initial conditions of the problem. An infinite number of mode shapes u_j and corresponding natural frequencies ω_j are associated with the resolution of Eq. (51). The higher the number of superimposed mode shapes is, the better the accuracy of the solution is (taking into consideration the frequency range of validity of the model) (KELLY, 2011).

Prescribed BCs of a vibrating rod should be considered in addition to Eq. (51) in order to form a BVP and construct its analytical solution. The most common classical and non-classical BCs for mode shapes of rods are presented in Table 1 for a generic boundary l_i . Here, $ES u^{(1)}$ denotes the stress, b_i stands for a constant which assumes the values $b_1 = -1$ and $b_2 = 1$ for the left ($x = l_1$) and right ($x = l_2$) ends of the rod, $\mathcal{V}_i = K_{i,T} + j(\rho/E)^{\frac{1}{2}} m_i \lambda$ for the general non-classical BC, where $K_{i,T}$ is the stiffness of a translational spring and m_i is an attached mass, both placed at the boundary l_i , and j is the imaginary unit (INMAN, 2013; GROVER, 1972).

Table 1: Classical and non-classical BCs for rods

BC	Expression at $x = l_i$
clamped	$u _{x=l_i} = 0$
free	$ES u^{(1)} _{x=l_i} = 0$
general non-classical BC	$ES u^{(1)} _{x=l_i} + b_i \mathcal{V}_i u _{x=l_i} = 0$

Source: Prepared by the author.

¹²Purely longitudinal waves only propagate in unbounded solid media when the two perpendicular motion directions are sizable. Once the rod's model assumes exclusive longitudinal vibration for thin structures, the term *quasi*-longitudinal wavenumber is more accurate. (FAHY, 2006).

3.2 TRANSVERSAL VIBRATION OF EULER-BERNOULLI BEAMS

The Euler-Bernoulli beam theory is also referred to as the classical beam theory and has great importance in the solution of vibration problems. The beam model described by this theory deals with transverse vibrations of slender structures and the underlying assumptions of neglecting both the shearing effect and the rotational inertia in the cross-section are suitable. In particular, these assumptions are reasonable for beams whose cross-sectional dimensions are small compared to the wavelength, and then the lateral motion can be found as negligible (MEIROVITCH, 2010; KINSLER *et al.*, 1999).

A beam undergoing free transverse vibration is modelled in accordance with the Euler-Bernoulli beam theory by the following PDE (INMAN, 2013; WANG; REDDY; LEE, 2000):

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \left(EI \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{u}}{\partial x^2} \right) + \rho S \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{u}}{\partial t^2} = 0, \quad x \in]l_1, l_2[, \quad t > 0, \quad (52)$$

where E is the Young's modulus, I is the cross-sectional area moment of inertia, ρ is the density of the beam and S is the cross-sectional area function. The transverse displacement is given by $\tilde{u} = \tilde{u}(x, t)$, $x \in [l_1, l_2]$ is the position along the beam and $t \geq 0$ represents time.

Similarly to the above-mentioned case for rods, the introduction of an harmonic solution in the motion equation leads to the mode shape equation for $u = u(x)$. In this case, Eq. (52) yields the following ODE for non-uniform beams with constant material properties (GERADIN, 2015):

$$u^{(4)} + 2 \frac{I^{(1)}}{I} u^{(3)} + \frac{I^{(2)}}{I} u^{(2)} - \frac{\rho S \omega^2}{EI} u = 0, \quad (53)$$

for $I = I(x)$ and $S = S(x)$. If one admits a uniform beam, in which all of its cross-sectional parameters are given as constants, Eq. (53) becomes (CLOUGH, 2003; KINSLER *et al.*, 1999):

$$u^{(4)} - \lambda^4 u = 0, \quad (54)$$

where $\lambda = (\rho S \omega^2 / EI)^{\frac{1}{4}}$ is the wavenumber. The general solution of Eq. (54) is usually formulated in this way (BLEVINS, 2001; WEAVER; TIMOSHENKO; YOUNG, 1990; GROVER, 1972):

$$u = \mathcal{A}_1 \sinh(\lambda x) + \mathcal{A}_2 \cosh(\lambda x) + \mathcal{A}_3 \sin(\lambda x) + \mathcal{A}_4 \cos(\lambda x), \quad (55)$$

for the real constants \mathcal{A}_1 , \mathcal{A}_2 , \mathcal{A}_3 , and \mathcal{A}_4 . Here, and without loss of generality, the assumption has been made that $\mathcal{A}_4 = 1$. In essence, solutions for the transversal vibration of Euler-Bernoulli beams can be obtained via superposition of mode shapes by the same means of the rod case. A given mode j can be characterized by the following mode shape function (and its corresponding natural angular frequency ω_j and wavenumber λ_j):

$$u_j = \mathcal{A}_1(\omega_j) \sinh(\lambda_j x) + \mathcal{A}_2(\omega_j) \cosh(\lambda_j x) + \mathcal{A}_3(\omega_j) \sin(\lambda_j x) + \cos(\lambda_j x). \quad (56)$$

The analysis of vibration mode shapes of beams that could be subject to various kinds of BCs is crucial for understanding the dynamic behavior of slender structures. Table 2 presents some general expressions of BCs for Euler-Bernoulli beams. Here, $u^{(1)}$, $EI u^{(2)}$ and $-EI u^{(3)}$ denote, respectively, slope, bending moment and shearing force (WEAVER; TIMOSHENKO; YOUNG, 1990). Those BCs are expressed at $x = l_1, l_2$, i.e., at the left or right end of a beam. For added impedances, translational and rotational stiffnesses are denoted by $K_{i,T}$ and $K_{i,R}$, respectively, translational masses are given by m_i and rotational inertias by J_i , $\mathcal{M}_i = -K_{i,R} + (EI/\rho S) J_i \lambda^4$ and $\mathcal{V}_i = -K_{i,T} + (EI/\rho S) m_i \lambda^4$ (KARNOVSKY; LEBED, 2004; WANG; REDDY; LEE, 2000). Equivalently to the rod case, $b_1 = -1$ and $b_2 = 1$ represent the convention for positive and negative signs at the left and the right ends of the beam, respectively.

Table 2: Classical and non-classical BCs for Euler-Bernoulli beams

BC	Expression at $x = l_i$
clamped	$u _{x=l_i} = 0$ and $u^{(1)} _{x=l_i} = 0$
free	$EI u^{(2)} _{x=l_i} = 0$ and $-EI u^{(3)} _{x=l_i} = 0$
pinned	$u _{x=l_i} = 0$ and $EI u^{(2)} _{x=l_i} = 0$
sliding	$u^{(1)} _{x=l_i} = 0$ and $-EI u^{(3)} _{x=l_i} = 0$
general non-classical BC	$EI u^{(2)} _{x=l_i} = b_i \mathcal{M}_i u^{(1)} _{x=l_i}$ and $-EI u^{(3)} _{x=l_i} = b_i \mathcal{V}_i u _{x=l_i}$

Source: Prepared by the author.

Exact solutions that result from the BCs of a beam and Eq. (55) are usually prone to round-off errors when numerically evaluated at high frequencies ω_j . This might be explained since the functions $\sinh(\lambda_j l_i)$ and $\cosh(\lambda_j l_i)$ ($l_i = l_1, l_2$) are becoming to be closely similar, i.e., with the same asymptotic behavior as their exponential growth follows the frequency increasing, and operations between them cannot be accurately assessed by floating-point arithmetic¹³. As such, the four equations from the beam BCs are likely to

¹³Numerical operations such as subtracting closer values may produce meaningless results due to the

yield inaccurate values for ω_j , \mathcal{A}_1 , \mathcal{A}_2 , and \mathcal{A}_3 .

3.3 TRANSVERSAL VIBRATION OF TIMOSHENKO BEAMS

The Timoshenko beam model¹⁴ includes effects of shearing forces and rotatory inertia in comparison to the Euler-Bernoulli model (LOVE, 2013). Thus, the inertia of the sections is no longer concentrated at the center of the beam and the transverse shear is built in the model, which requires a correction on account of the assumption of constant shear stress along the beam's cross-section. This correction is given by the so-called shear factor κ , whose value depends on properties of the beam such as its geometry and material (WANG; REDDY; LEE, 2000; HUTCHINSON, 2000; TIMOSHENKO, 1922).

Once this beam model considers cross-sectional rotation, one might expect more elaborate describing DEs. The motion equations of a free Timoshenko beam undergoing transverse vibration is written as (GERADIN, 2015; INMAN, 2013):

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[SG\kappa \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{u}}{\partial x} - \tilde{\phi} \right) \right] - \rho S \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{u}}{\partial t^2} = 0, \quad (57)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(EI \frac{\partial \tilde{\phi}}{\partial x} \right) + SG\kappa \left(\frac{\partial \tilde{u}}{\partial x} - \tilde{\phi} \right) - \rho I \frac{\partial^2 \tilde{\phi}}{\partial t^2} = 0, \quad x \in]l_1, l_2[, t > 0, \quad (58)$$

where S is the cross-sectional area, G and E are respectively the shear and Young's modulus, I is the cross-sectional area moment of inertia and ρ is the density. $\tilde{u} = \tilde{u}(x, t)$ stands for the transverse displacement, $\tilde{\phi} = \tilde{\phi}(x, t)$ is the cross-sectional's rotation, composed by the rotation due to bending and the shear angle, $x \in [l_1, l_2]$ is the position along the beam and $t \geq 0$ denotes time.

Considering harmonic solutions for Eqs. (57) and (58) just as $\tilde{u} = u e^{i\omega t}$ and $\tilde{\phi} = \phi e^{i\omega t}$ and all beam parameters as constants, this yields (CAZZANI; STOCHINO; TURCO, 2016):

$$u^{(2)} - \phi^{(1)} + \lambda^2 \phi = 0, \quad (59)$$

complete cancellation of significant digits, see (GOLDBERG, 1991) and (WILKINSON, 1994) for cancellation errors explanation in floating-point arithmetic.

¹⁴Recent research suggest Timoshenko-Ehrenfest beam theory as "fairer" name for this theory (ELISHAKOFF, 2019).

and

$$\beta \phi^{(2)} + \gamma (u^{(1)} - \phi) + \lambda^2 \phi = 0, \quad (60)$$

for $\beta = E/G\kappa$, $\gamma = A/I$ and $\lambda = (\rho/G\kappa)^{\frac{1}{2}} \omega$, where the mode shapes are represented by $u = u(x)$ and $\phi = \phi(x)$.

Closed-form solutions for the mode shapes of Timoshenko beams can be found through the resolution of an eigenvalue problem (see (GEIST; MCLAUGHLIN, 1997), for instance). Based on this, three distinct expressions can represent each mode shapes function u and ϕ . In essence, these separate cases arise from the existence of real and complex roots for a given nontrivial eigenvalue solution, which depend on the properties of the beam, embraced by the parameter γ , and the range of natural frequencies considered in the analysis. Thus, if $\lambda^2 > \gamma$, then (KHASAWNEH; SEGALMAN, 2019; CAZZANI; STOCHINO; TURCO, 2016):

$$\begin{bmatrix} u \\ \phi \end{bmatrix} = \mathcal{A}_1 \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\tilde{\lambda}_1 x) \\ -\frac{\lambda^2 - \tilde{\lambda}_1^2}{\tilde{\lambda}_1} \cos(\tilde{\lambda}_1 x) \end{bmatrix} + \mathcal{A}_2 \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\tilde{\lambda}_1 x) \\ \frac{\lambda^2 - \tilde{\lambda}_1^2}{\tilde{\lambda}_1} \sin(\tilde{\lambda}_1 x) \end{bmatrix} + \mathcal{A}_3 \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\tilde{\lambda}_2 x) \\ -\frac{\lambda^2 - \tilde{\lambda}_2^2}{\tilde{\lambda}_2} \cos(\tilde{\lambda}_2 x) \end{bmatrix} + \mathcal{A}_4 \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\tilde{\lambda}_2 x) \\ \frac{\lambda^2 - \tilde{\lambda}_2^2}{\tilde{\lambda}_2} \sin(\tilde{\lambda}_2 x) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (61)$$

for the constants \mathcal{A}_1 , \mathcal{A}_2 , \mathcal{A}_3 , and \mathcal{A}_4 together with the real quantities $\tilde{\lambda}_1$ and $\tilde{\lambda}_2$, known as generalized wavenumbers:

$$\tilde{\lambda}_1 = \left[-\frac{\lambda^2}{2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) (\Delta^{\frac{1}{2}} - 1) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}, \quad (62)$$

and

$$\tilde{\lambda}_2 = \left[\frac{\lambda^2}{2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) (\Delta^{\frac{1}{2}} + 1) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (63)$$

When $\lambda^2 = \gamma$, the mode shape expressions assume the form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u \\ \phi \end{bmatrix} = \mathcal{A}_1 \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} + \mathcal{A}_2 \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ \gamma x \end{bmatrix} + \mathcal{A}_3 \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\tilde{\lambda}_2 x) \\ -\frac{\lambda^2 - \tilde{\lambda}_2^2}{\tilde{\lambda}_2} \cos(\tilde{\lambda}_2 x) \end{bmatrix} + \mathcal{A}_4 \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\tilde{\lambda}_2 x) \\ \frac{\lambda^2 - \tilde{\lambda}_2^2}{\tilde{\lambda}_2} \sin(\tilde{\lambda}_2 x) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (64)$$

and, if $\lambda^2 < \gamma$, these expressions become:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u \\ \phi \end{bmatrix} = \mathcal{A}_1 \begin{bmatrix} \sinh(\tilde{\lambda}_3 x) \\ \frac{\lambda^2 + \tilde{\lambda}_3^2}{\tilde{\lambda}_3} \cosh(\tilde{\lambda}_3 x) \end{bmatrix} + \mathcal{A}_2 \begin{bmatrix} \cosh(\tilde{\lambda}_3 x) \\ \frac{\lambda^2 + \tilde{\lambda}_3^2}{\tilde{\lambda}_3} \sinh(\tilde{\lambda}_3 x) \end{bmatrix} + \mathcal{A}_3 \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\tilde{\lambda}_2 x) \\ -\frac{\lambda^2 - \tilde{\lambda}_2^2}{\tilde{\lambda}_2} \cos(\tilde{\lambda}_2 x) \end{bmatrix} + \mathcal{A}_4 \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\tilde{\lambda}_2 x) \\ \frac{\lambda^2 - \tilde{\lambda}_2^2}{\tilde{\lambda}_2} \sin(\tilde{\lambda}_2 x) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (65)$$

where

$$\tilde{\lambda}_3 = \left[\frac{\lambda^2}{2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\beta} \right) (\Delta^{\frac{1}{2}} - 1) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (66)$$

Finally, the constant Δ for the generalized wavenumbers of Eqs. (62), (63), and (66) is defined as follows (RENSBURG; MERWE, 2006):

$$\Delta = 1 - \frac{4\beta}{(1 + \beta)^2} \left(1 - \frac{\gamma}{\lambda^2}\right). \quad (67)$$

Equivalently to the Euler-Bernoulli beam case, one can make the assumption of $\mathcal{A}_4 = 1$ with no loss of generality. Then, \mathcal{A}_1 , \mathcal{A}_2 , \mathcal{A}_3 , and λ follow from the boundary conditions of the beam for the three sets of closed-form solutions ($\lambda^2 > \gamma$, $\lambda^2 = \gamma$, and $\lambda^2 < \gamma$). Notice that Eq. (65) is prone to round-off errors alike Eq. (55) for small wavelengths within its admitted frequency range ($\tilde{\lambda}_3 \propto \lambda$), i.e., as operations between hyperbolic terms lead to inaccurate floating-point values.

The corrections provided by the introduction of shearing force and rotatory inertia effects in the beam model may be significant in the study of high-frequency vibration modes, when the lateral motion becomes prominent (XU *et al.*, 2019; SMITH, 2008). Otherwise, the account of these effects does not produce substantial changes in the accuracy of the vibrating behavior prediction at low frequencies in comparison with the Euler-Bernoulli beam model, especially for thin beams (ZHANG; THOMPSON; SHENG, 2020). Theories with order higher than three are seldom used due to the fact that the increased effort for solving their equations, in general, does not translate into a notable gain in the accuracy (REDDY, 2007; WANG; REDDY; LEE, 2000; LEVINSON, 1981).

3.4 PARTIAL REMARKS

Classical vibrating models of rods and beams were presented in this chapter. For the transverse vibration of beams, both Euler-Bernoulli and Timoshenko models were described. In the latter, the motion equation for non-uniform rods vibrating in the longitudinal direction was presented, deriving its mode shape equation and displaying some admitted BCs. Additionally, this chapter presented a discussion about mode shape solutions formulated via classical approaches for these models.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents Lie symmetry applications in the computation of exact mode shape functions of vibrating rods and beams. In the former, an order reduction is considered for the mode shape equation of longitudinally vibrating rods with arbitrary varying cross-sectional area functions. Additional Lie symmetries and closed-form solutions are found for specific cross-sectional area functions, and canonical coordinates are used for converting the reduced-order equation into quadratures. Also, this chapter brings the computation of numerically stable mode shapes of Euler-Bernoulli beams via Lie symmetries for all frequency range. Finally, the mode shape equations of the Timoshenko beam model are considered, and successive reductions of the order are performed to obtain reduced but equivalent equations. The symbolic computations shown in this report were carried out by computer algebra. The referring algorithms will be available in the final version of the dissertation.

4.1 MODE SHAPES OF RODS WITH VARYING CROSS-SECTIONS

In the first place, let $\xi = \xi(x, u)$ and $\eta = \eta(x, u)$ ($n_d = 1$) be the infinitesimal functions associated to point transformations such as Eq. (7) for the (x, u) -space of variables and Eqs. (11) and (13) for the extended transformations. These infinitesimal functions and the corresponding prolonged ones may represent admitted Lie symmetries of Eq. (51), the mode shape equation of rods with varying cross-sections. Accordingly, a second-order prolonged infinitesimal generator from Eq. (16) follows as:

$${}_{(2)}\mathcal{X} = \xi \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \eta \frac{\partial}{\partial u} + {}_{(1)}\eta \frac{\partial}{\partial u^{(1)}} + {}_{(2)}\eta \frac{\partial}{\partial u^{(2)}}. \quad (68)$$

This prolonged infinitesimal generator suits the infinitesimal criterion of Eq. (18) for Eq. (51), which yields the following system of determining equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial u^2} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial u^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x \partial u} + 2 \frac{S^{(1)}}{S} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial u} &= 0, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 \xi}{\partial x^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial x \partial u} - \frac{S^{(1)}}{S} \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} - 3 \lambda^2 u \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial u} - \left[S^{(2)} - \frac{(S^{(1)})^2}{S} \right] \frac{\xi}{S} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial x^2} + \lambda^2 u \left(2 \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial u} \right) + \frac{S^{(1)}}{S} \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x} + \lambda^2 \eta &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (69)$$

The solutions of the system from Eq. (69), i.e., the admitted Lie symmetries, are given in Table 3. In this instance, one may notice that \mathcal{X}_2 represents a symmetry that depends on the specification of the function S to be explicitly computed. It was chosen to symbolize its infinitesimal functions by the functions Θ_1 and Θ_2 .

Table 3: Lie point symmetries of the mode shape equation of rods with varying cross-sections

\mathcal{X}_i	$\xi_{(i)}$	$\eta_{(i)}$
\mathcal{X}_1	0	u
\mathcal{X}_2	$\Theta_1(x, u, S)$	$\Theta_2(x, u, S)$

Source: Prepared by the author.

4.1.1 Reduced-order equation for arbitrary cross-sectional area functions

From the reduction procedure of Section 2.5, Chapter 2, the invariance relations for \mathcal{X}_1 are expressed in the form:

$$\mathcal{X}_1\{r(x, u)\} = 0, \quad (1)\mathcal{X}_1\{v(x, u, u^{(1)})\} = 0, \quad (70)$$

and

$${}_{(2)}\mathcal{X}_1\{v^{(1)}(x, u, u^{(1)}, u^{(2)})\} = 0, \quad (71)$$

for the invariants r , v and $v^{(1)}$, which gives the following characteristic equation:

$$\frac{dx}{\xi_{(1)}} = \frac{du}{\eta_{(1)}} = \frac{du^{(1)}}{{}_{(1)}\eta_{(1)}} = \frac{du^{(2)}}{{}_{(2)}\eta_{(1)}}, \quad (72)$$

where the prolonged infinitesimal functions are ${}_{(1)}\eta_{(1)} = u^{(1)}$ and ${}_{(2)}\eta_{(1)} = u^{(2)}$ from Eqs. (12) and (14), respectively. The resolution of Eq. (72) define the set of differential invariants:

$$\left\{ r = x, v = \frac{u^{(1)}}{u}, v^{(1)} = \frac{u^{(2)}}{u} - \left(\frac{u^{(1)}}{u} \right)^2 \right\}. \quad (73)$$

A change of variables can be performed using the computed invariants for reducing

the order of Eq. (51), i.e., isolating $u^{(2)}$ from $v^{(1)}$, $u^{(1)}$ from v in addition to $r = x$ and substituting these expressions into the original ODE (one may notice that any remaining dependency on the $(x, u, u^{(1)}, u^{(2)})$ -space is left by this procedure). Therefore, the following Riccati equation is obtained:

$$v^{(1)} + v^2 + \frac{S^{(1)}}{S} v + \lambda^2 = 0, \quad (74)$$

for $v = v(r)$ and $S = S(r)$ mentioned above. It is worth noticing that this first-order equation can replace the second-order Eq. (51) due to the existence of an admitted Lie symmetry transformation that, fundamentally, keeps the solution of the original equation.

The reduced-order equation Eq. (74) brings new alternatives for computing mode shapes of rods with varying cross-sections. The first one consists in solving it via standard methods for Riccati equations (SIMMONS, 1991; TENENBAUM; POLLARD, 1985; BOYCE; DIPRIMA; MEADE, 2018) and, hence, finding closed-form solutions for vibrating rods. The second option lies in the computation of additional Lie symmetries, i.e., \mathcal{X}_2 or extra symmetries, which require the specification of the analytic function for the cross-sectional area. In addition to that, invariant BVPs can be assessed through the invariance formulation for them. The following examples illustrate the two first alternatives for specific cross-sectional area functions.

4.1.2 Example 1: closed-form solution for the reduced-order equation, rod with the cross-sectional area function $S = (a_1 + a_2 x)^{a_3}$

A rod with the cross-sectional area function given by $S = (a_1 + a_2 x)^{a_3}$ is considered in this example, just as the first reported case in Li (2000). The following ODE is obtained by taking Eq. (74) and the cross-sectional area expression as follows:

$$v^{(1)} + v^2 + \frac{a_2 a_3}{a_1 + a_2 r} v + \lambda^2 = 0, \quad (75)$$

whose solution is given by:

$$v = \ln \left\{ \mathbf{I}_{\frac{1}{2}(a_3-1)} \left[-j \left(\frac{a_1}{a_2} + r \right) \lambda \right] - \mathcal{C}_1 \mathbf{K}_{\frac{1}{2}(a_3-1)} \left[-j \left(\frac{a_1}{a_2} + r \right) \lambda \right] \right\} + \frac{1-a_3}{2} \ln(a_1 + a_2 r), \quad (76)$$

in which the invariant relations $v = u^{(1)}/u$ and $r = x$ from Eq. (73) lead to the closed-form expression for mode shapes of the rod:

$$u = (a_1 + a_2 x)^{-\frac{1}{2}(a_3-1)} \mathcal{C}_2 \left\{ \mathcal{C}_1 \mathbf{K}_{\frac{1}{2}(a_3-1)} \left[-j \left(\frac{a_1}{a_2} + x \right) \lambda \right] - \mathbf{I}_{\frac{1}{2}(a_3-1)} \left[-j \left(\frac{a_1}{a_2} + x \right) \lambda \right] \right\}, \quad (77)$$

for K and I being modified Bessel functions of first and second kind, respectively, and \mathcal{C}_1 and \mathcal{C}_2 being constants of integration. This closed-form solution is equivalent to the one presented in Li (2000), although computed via the Lie symmetry method and described by modified Bessel functions.

4.1.3 Example 2: resolution via quadrature of the reduced-order equation, rod with the cross-sectional area function $S = a_1 a_2^{a_3 x}$

If the Lie symmetries of Table 3 (\mathcal{X}_1 , \mathcal{X}_2 and extra infinitesimal generators, if there are any additional symmetries) form a solvable Lie algebra¹⁵, the remaining unused symmetries are still admitted by Eq. (74) after the first reduction of order and the Riccati equation can be turned into a quadrature through the introduction of canonical coordinates (GONZÁLEZ-LÓPEZ, 1988; OLVER, 1986). As an example, let $S = a_1 a_2^{a_3 x}$ be the cross-sectional area function of a non-uniform rod. In this case, the system of determining equations from Eq. (69) admits the additional pair of infinitesimal functions $\xi_{(2)} = 1$ and $\eta_{(2)} = 0$, which gives the infinitesimal generator $\mathcal{X}_2 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x}$. This non-prolonged generator can be mapped to the (r, v) -space of variables by the relations of Eq. (30) for the set of invariants of Eq. (73) as follows:

$$\mathcal{X}_2 = \frac{\partial}{\partial r}. \quad (78)$$

In reference to the accomplishment of a quadrature from Eq. (74), the following canonical coordinates R and $V = V(R)$ can be introduced:

$$R = v, \quad V = r, \quad (79)$$

which are associated to the infinitesimal generator of Eq. (78) for the solution of Eqs. (46) and (47). A change of coordinates from the $(r, v, v^{(1)})$ -space of variables to the canonical one¹⁶ leads to the quadrature:

$$V^{(1)} + R^2 + \ln(a_2) a_3 R + \lambda^2 = 0, \quad (80)$$

where $V^{(1)} = \frac{dV}{dR}$ simply follows from the chain rule for $x = r$:

$$V^{(1)} = \frac{dV}{dR} \frac{dx}{dx} = \frac{1}{v^{(1)}}. \quad (81)$$

¹⁵Recall that two-dimensional algebras are always solvable (BLUMAN, 1990).

¹⁶The change of coordinates of Eq. (79) are related to hodograph transformations (BOCHAROV, 1999).

From this, the resolution of Eq. (80) yields the closed-form solution:

$$V = -\frac{2}{A} \arctan \left(\frac{2R + \ln(a_2) a_3}{A} \right) + \mathcal{C}_1, \quad (82)$$

where $A = \sqrt{4\lambda^2 - \ln(a_2)^2 a_3^2}$ and \mathcal{C}_1 is a constant of integration. Finally, this expression is written in terms of the invariants of Eq. (73) through the inverse canonical transformation ($r = V$ and $v = R$) and, then, integrated for $\frac{u^{(1)}}{u} = v$ in order to provide the closed-form solution:

$$u = \mathcal{C}_1 a_2^{-\frac{a_3}{2}x} \cos \left[\frac{A}{2}(x - \mathcal{C}_1) \right] + \mathcal{C}_2. \quad (83)$$

for \mathcal{C}_2 being a constant of integration.

4.1.4 Invariant boundary value problems

The invariance formulation for BVPs establishes whether its BCs are invariant or not under a Lie group or subgroup. By taking \mathcal{X}_1 in Eqs. (48) and (49) for the BCs of Table 1, it can be investigated how these constrained variables may fit the reduced-order space of variables spawned by Eq. (73). For any boundary condition at $x = l_i$, Eq. (48) yields:

$$\mathcal{X}_1\{x - l_i\} = u \frac{\partial}{\partial u}(x - l_i) = 0 \quad \text{when } x = l_i \quad (i = 1, 2). \quad (84)$$

A clamped end l_i requires null displacement, i.e., $u|_{x=l_i} = 0$. For this, Eq. (49) gives:

$$\mathcal{X}_1\{u\}|_{x=l_i} = u \frac{\partial}{\partial u} u|_{x=l_i} = 0 \quad \text{when } u|_{x=l_i} = 0 \text{ and } x = l_i, \quad (85)$$

which holds true. Then, the clamped BC is converted to the reduced-space by the invariants of Eq. (73) as follows:

$$v|_{r=l_i} = \infty. \quad (86)$$

For first-order BCs such as free ends, it is essential to employ the first-prolonged version of \mathcal{X}_1 in the invariance condition (notice that the clamped constrain only required the non-prolonged version of the infinitesimal generator). In this case, Eq. (49) gives:

$${}_{(1)}\mathcal{X}_1\{u^{(1)}\}|_{x=l_i} = u \frac{\partial}{\partial u} u^{(1)}|_{x=l_i} + u^{(1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial u^{(1)}} u^{(1)}|_{x=l_i} = 0 \quad \text{when } u^{(1)}|_{x=l_i} = 0 \text{ and } x = l_i, \quad (87)$$

and the corresponding mapped BC from $v = u^{(1)}/u$ at $x = l_i$ is:

$$v|_{r=l_i} = 0. \quad (88)$$

General non-classical BCs yield the invariance expression from Eq. (49):

$${}_{(1)}\mathcal{X}_1\{ES u^{(1)} + b_i \mathcal{V}_i u\}|_{x=l_i} = 0 \quad \text{when} \quad ES u^{(1)}|_{x=l_i} + b_i \mathcal{V}_i u|_{x=l_i} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad x=l_i, \quad (89)$$

whose evaluation leads to:

$$u \frac{\partial}{\partial u}(ES u^{(1)} + b_i \mathcal{V}_i u)|_{x=l_i} + u^{(1)} \frac{\partial}{\partial u^{(1)}}(ES u^{(1)} + b_i \mathcal{V}_i u)|_{x=l_i} = 0. \quad (90)$$

Writing Eq. (90) in terms of the admitted invariants results in:

$$ES v|_{r=l_i} + b_i \mathcal{V}_i = 0, \quad (91)$$

then

$$v|_{r=l_i} = -\frac{b_i \mathcal{V}_i}{ES(l_i)}. \quad (92)$$

Eqs. (86), (88), and (92) represent the BCs from Table 1 in the new space of variables of the corresponding Riccati equation. The example in the sequence illustrates the utilization of these boundary conditions, invariant under the symmetry transformation from \mathcal{X}_1 . Additionally, the example brings the wavenumber computation and mode shape expressions for a rod with varying cross-sectional area.

4.1.5 Example 3: mode shapes from reduced-order boundary value problems, rod with the cross-sectional area function $S = a_1 x + a_2 x^3$

For this example, let $S = a_1 x + a_2 x^3$ be the cross-sectional area function of a free-free rod, in which $l_1 = 0$ and $l_2 = l$. The reduced-order ODE from Eq. (74) and the left-end BC for the rod follow as:

$$v^{(1)} + v^2 + \frac{a_1 + 3a_2 r^2}{r(a_1 + a_2 r^2)} v + \lambda^2 = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad v|_{r=0} = 0. \quad (93)$$

The symbolic solution for the BVP of Eq. (93) has the form:

$$v = -2 \frac{a_2 r H'_c\left(0, 0, 0, -\frac{a_1 \lambda^2}{4 a_2}, \frac{a_1 \lambda^2}{4 a_2}, -\frac{a_2 r^2}{a_1}\right)}{a_1 H_c\left(0, 0, 0, -\frac{a_1 \lambda^2}{4 a_2}, \frac{a_1 \lambda^2}{4 a_2}, -\frac{a_2 r^2}{a_1}\right)}, \quad (94)$$

where H_c is the Heun Confluent function and H'_c is its first derivative (see (HEUN, 1888; FILIPUK; ISHKHANYAN; DEREZIŃSKI, 2020) for the definition of Heun functions and its derivatives and (MAIER, 2006) for 192 admitted solutions, computed by use of symmetry groups).

Mode shape solutions are obtained for this rod by a change of variables in Eq. (94) from the invariant space to the original coordinates, with the relations of Eq. (73), and integrating the resulting equation, which gives:

$$u = \mathcal{C}_2 H_c \left(0, 0, 0, -\frac{a_1 \lambda^2}{4 a_2}, \frac{a_1 \lambda^2}{4 a_2}, -\frac{a_2 x^2}{a_1} \right), \quad (95)$$

for the constant of integration \mathcal{C}_2 computed via the remaining BC of the free-free rod, i.e., $u^{(1)}|_{x=l} = 0$. From this, Eq. (95) becomes:

$$\mathcal{C}_2 H'_c \left(0, 0, 0, -\frac{a_1 \lambda^2}{4 a_2}, \frac{a_1 \lambda^2}{4 a_2}, -\frac{a_2 l^2}{a_1} \right) = 0, \quad (96)$$

where $\mathcal{C}_2 \neq 0$ in order not to have a trivial solution. Thus, it was set $\mathcal{C}_2 = 1$ and the related frequency equation¹⁷ follows from:

$$H'_c \left(0, 0, 0, -\frac{a_1 \lambda^2}{4 a_2}, \frac{a_1 \lambda^2}{4 a_2}, -\frac{a_2 l^2}{a_1} \right) = 0. \quad (97)$$

The first four solutions of the transcendental equation of Eq. (97) are displayed in Table 4, computed by iterative root-finding algorithms. The corresponding mode shape functions of the rod illustrated in Figure 1 are plotted in Figure 2 for the cross-sectional parameters $a_1 = -0.2$ m and $a_2 = 0.15$ m⁻¹ of a rod with length $l = 1$ m.

Figure 1: Sketch of a free-free rod with the cross-sectional area $S = -0.2x + 0.15x^3$

Table 4: First four wavenumbers of a rod with the cross-sectional area $S = -0.2x + 0.15x^3$

n	1	2	3	4
$\lambda_n l$	4.009642	7.156431	10.285374	13.415313

Source: Prepared by the author.

¹⁷The resolution of transcendental equations such as frequency equations usually relies on root-finding algorithms by iterations (MULLER, 1956; KELLEY, 1995), however graphical (SINGH, 2011) and non-conventional methods (JESWAL; CHAKRAVERTY, 2018; PEROVICH *et al.*, 2007) are also applied.

Figure 2: First four mode shapes of a free-free rod with the cross-sectional area function $S = -0.2x + 0.15x^3$, computed via the Lie symmetry approach

4.2 MODE SHAPES OF UNIFORM EULER-BERNOULLI BEAMS

This section is concerned with computing numerically stable mode shape functions of uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams via the Lie symmetry method. In particular, classical and non-classical BCs are evaluated under the invariance formulation for BVPs to provide exact solutions for the mode shapes of Euler-Bernoulli beams with several boundary configurations. Developed in collaboration with Prof. Dr. Jean-Mathieu Mencik (INSA Centre Val de Loire) and Prof. Dr. Paulo J. Paupitz Gonçalves (UNESP), this section's subject has been submitted to the Acta Mechanica Journal in the form of a manuscript.

In short, the closed-form solution of Eq. (55) becomes inaccurate for the numerical assessment as the wavelength becomes small (high frequencies) due to round-off errors. A strategy for obtaining new closed-form expressions, and, alternatively, numerically stable ones, consists in seeking transformations for the mode shape equation of Euler-Bernoulli beams that express BVPs for beams in suitable spaces of variables, e.g., through the Lie symmetry method (YANG; HUA, 2014; ZHANG; LI, 2020). This approach for accomplish-

ing suitable spaces for the numerical evaluation is described in the following. A Lie group of point transformations for the mode shape equation of uniform beams, Eq (54), admits the infinitesimal functions $\xi = \xi(x, u)$ and $\eta = \eta(x, u)$. Here, these functions and their associated infinitesimal generator must be prolonged to act on the $(x, u, u^{(1)}, u^{(2)}, u^{(3)}, u^{(4)})$ -space of variables in accordance with Eq. (16). Then, the infinitesimal criterion of Eq. (18) leads to the following system of determining equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^4 \eta}{\partial x^4} + \left(u \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial u} - \eta \right) \lambda^4 &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial x \partial u} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial^2 \eta}{\partial u^2} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial u} &= 0, \end{aligned} \tag{98}$$

whose solutions are represented in Table 5. Once the problem under consideration admits six linearly independent infinitesimal generators, one can set a 6-parameter Lie group represented by the general infinitesimal generator of the form:

$$\mathcal{X} = \left(u + \alpha_1 e^{\lambda x} + \alpha_2 e^{-\lambda x} + \alpha_3 \sin(\lambda x) + \alpha_4 \cos(\lambda x) \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial u} + \alpha_5 \frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \tag{99}$$

where the constants $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4$ and α_5 are named as transformation parameters.

Table 5: Lie point symmetries of the mode shape equation of uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams

\mathcal{X}_i	$\xi_{(i)}$	$\eta_{(i)}$
\mathcal{X}_1	0	u
\mathcal{X}_2	1	0
\mathcal{X}_3	0	$e^{\lambda x}$
\mathcal{X}_4	0	$e^{-\lambda x}$
\mathcal{X}_5	0	$\sin(\lambda x)$
\mathcal{X}_6	0	$\cos(\lambda x)$

Source: Prepared by the author.

The invariance conditions of Eqs. (48) and (49) have to be considered in order to obtain a fully invariant BVP under the symmetry transformation of Eq. (99). For the

former, the condition becomes:

$$\mathcal{X}\{x - l_i\} = 0 \quad \text{when } x = l_i \quad (i = 1, 2), \quad (100)$$

which gives $\alpha_5 = 0$. Moreover, Eq. (49) gives the additional condition. For instance, for zero-order BCs such as $u|_{x=l_i} = 0$, Eq. (49) yields:

$$\mathcal{X}\{u\}|_{x=l_i} = 0 \quad \text{when } u|_{x=l_i} = 0. \quad (101)$$

from where the following restriction equation arises:

$$\alpha_1 e^{\lambda l_i} + \alpha_2 e^{-\lambda l_i} + \alpha_3 \sin(\lambda l_i) + \alpha_4 \cos(\lambda l_i) = 0. \quad (102)$$

Table 6 provides the invariance conditions and their associated restriction equations for all BCs displayed in Table 2 for Euler-Bernoulli beams. These conditions are written in short form for the sake of conciseness, which mould accords to Eq. (101). The prolonged infinitesimal generators, required for these relations, follow from Eq. (16).

Table 6: Invariance conditions for BCs of Euler-Bernoulli beams

Invariance condition ($x = l_i$)	Restriction equation
$\mathcal{X}\{u\}=0$	$\alpha_1 e^{\lambda l_i} + \alpha_2 e^{-\lambda l_i} + \alpha_3 \sin(\lambda l_i) + \alpha_4 \cos(\lambda l_i) = 0$
$(1)\mathcal{X}\{u^{(1)}\}=0$	$-\alpha_1 e^{\lambda l_i} + \alpha_2 e^{-\lambda l_i} - \alpha_3 \cos(\lambda l_i) + \alpha_4 \sin(\lambda l_i) = 0$
$(2)\mathcal{X}\{EI u^{(2)} - b_i \mathcal{M}_i u^{(1)} _{x=l_i}\}=0$	$\alpha_1 \left(\lambda - b_i \frac{\mathcal{M}_i}{EI} \right) e^{\lambda l_i} + \alpha_2 \left(\lambda + b_i \frac{\mathcal{M}_i}{EI} \right) e^{-\lambda l_i} - \left(\alpha_3 \lambda - \alpha_4 b_i \frac{\mathcal{M}_i}{EI} \right) \sin(\lambda l_i) - \left(\alpha_4 \lambda + \alpha_3 b_i \frac{\mathcal{M}_i}{EI} \right) \cos(\lambda l_i) = 0$
$(3)\mathcal{X}\{EI u^{(3)} + b_i \mathcal{V}_i u _{x=l_i}\}=0$	$\alpha_1 \left(\lambda^3 + b_i \frac{\mathcal{V}_i}{EI} \right) e^{\lambda l_i} - \alpha_2 \left(\lambda^3 - b_i \frac{\mathcal{V}_i}{EI} \right) e^{-\lambda l_i} + \left(\alpha_4 \lambda^3 + \alpha_3 b_i \frac{\mathcal{V}_i}{EI} \right) \sin(\lambda l_i) - \left(\alpha_3 \lambda^3 - \alpha_4 b_i \frac{\mathcal{V}_i}{EI} \right) \cos(\lambda l_i) = 0$

Source: Prepared by the author.

4.2.1 Canonical coordinates

Earlier it has been shown that the transformation parameter α_5 is equal to zero for any admitted BVP. In accordance to that, the canonical coordinates R and $V = V(R)$ for the symmetry transformation of Eq. (99), which result from solving the system of DEs from Eqs. (46) and (47), are:

$$R = x, \quad V = \lambda x + \ln \left(u + \alpha_1 e^{\lambda x} + \alpha_2 e^{-\lambda x} + \alpha_3 \sin(\lambda x) + \alpha_4 \cos(\lambda x) \right),$$

which results in the following displacement expression through the inverse canonical transformation, i.e., writing the original space of variables in terms of canonical coordinates:

$$u = e^{V-\lambda R} - \left(\alpha_1 e^{\lambda R} + \alpha_2 e^{-\lambda R} + \alpha_3 \sin(\lambda R) + \alpha_4 \cos(\lambda R) \right). \quad (103)$$

The substitution of Eq. (103) into the mode shape equation Eq. (54) with $x = R$ produces a DE written in the canonical domain, which closed-form solution is:

$$V = \ln \left[\frac{1}{4\lambda^3} \left(-\mathcal{C}_1 e^{2\lambda R} + \mathcal{C}_2 \right) + \frac{e^{\lambda R}}{2\lambda^3} \left(\mathcal{C}_3 \sin(\lambda R) - \mathcal{C}_4 \cos(\lambda R) \right) \right],$$

and from the inverse transformation:

$$u = - \left(\frac{\mathcal{C}_1}{4\lambda^3} + \alpha_1 \right) e^{\lambda x} + \left(\frac{\mathcal{C}_2}{4\lambda^3} - \alpha_2 \right) e^{-\lambda x} + \left(\frac{\mathcal{C}_3}{2\lambda^3} - \alpha_3 \right) \sin(\lambda x) - \left(\frac{\mathcal{C}_4}{2\lambda^3} + \alpha_4 \right) \cos(\lambda x). \quad (104)$$

A relevant solution can be obtained by setting constants \mathcal{C}_1 , \mathcal{C}_2 , \mathcal{C}_3 and \mathcal{C}_4 to zero, illustrated later in two examples. Then, the resulting closed-form expression of mode shape functions of Euler-Bernoulli beams follows as:

$$\bar{u} = -\alpha_1 e^{\lambda x} - \alpha_2 e^{-\lambda x} - \alpha_3 \sin(\lambda x) - \alpha_4 \cos(\lambda x). \quad (105)$$

Eq. (105) together with the restriction equations listed in Table 6 yield mode shape functions for Euler-Bernoulli beams subject to classical and non-classical undamped BCs. Within the framework of the proposed approach, the expressions of the ODE of the beam and the related BCs are “unified” by considering their invariance properties under the given symmetry transformation. Two examples are presented in the following for assessing mode shapes of beams with classical and non-classical BCs.

4.2.2 Example 1: mode shapes of a uniform clamped-free beam

Consider an Euler-Bernoulli beam clamped at $l_1 = 0$ and free at $l_2 = l$ as shown in Figure 3. In this case, the BCs are expressed by $u|_{x=0} = u^{(1)}|_{x=0} = 0$ (left end) and $u^{(2)}|_{x=l} = u^{(3)}|_{x=l} = 0$ (right end). The related restriction equations are obtained from Table 6, where $\mathcal{M}_i = \mathcal{V}_i = 0$ for $i = 1, 2$, i.e.:

Figure 3: Sketch of a uniform clamped-free beam

$$\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 + \alpha_4 = 0, \quad (106)$$

$$\alpha_1 - \alpha_2 + \alpha_3 = 0, \quad (107)$$

$$\alpha_1 e^{\lambda l} + \alpha_2 e^{-\lambda l} - \alpha_3 \sin(\lambda l) - \alpha_4 \cos(\lambda l) = 0, \quad (108)$$

$$\alpha_1 e^{\lambda l} - \alpha_2 e^{-\lambda l} - \alpha_3 \cos(\lambda l) + \alpha_4 \sin(\lambda l) = 0. \quad (109)$$

Here, the assumption of $\alpha_4 = 1$ has been made, then Eqs. (106 - 109) lead to the frequency equation:

$$\cos(\lambda l) (e^{\lambda l} + e^{-\lambda l}) + 2 = 0, \quad (110)$$

which can be multiplied by $e^{-\lambda l}$ in order to get a numerically stable equation (GONÇALVES; PEPLow; BRENNAN, 2018):

$$\cos(\lambda l)(1 + e^{-2\lambda l}) + 2e^{-\lambda l} = 0. \quad (111)$$

The roots $\lambda l = \lambda_j l$ of Eq. (111) are displayed in Table 7, obtained via iterations on root-finding algorithms, and the transformation parameters α_1 , α_2 and α_3 follow as:

$$\alpha_1 = -\frac{\sin(\lambda l) - \cos(\lambda l) - e^{-\lambda l}}{2 \sin(\lambda l) + e^{\lambda l} - e^{-\lambda l}}, \quad (112)$$

$$\alpha_2 = -\frac{\sin(\lambda l) + \cos(\lambda l) + e^{\lambda l}}{2 \sin(\lambda l) + e^{\lambda l} - e^{-\lambda l}}, \quad (113)$$

$$\alpha_3 = -\frac{2 \cos(\lambda l) + e^{\lambda l} + e^{-\lambda l}}{2 \sin(\lambda l) + e^{\lambda l} - e^{-\lambda l}}. \quad (114)$$

By considering Eqs. (112 - 114) together with $\alpha_4 = 1$ in Eq. (105), this yields the mode shapes of the clamped-free Euler-Bernoulli beam. One may easily check that these expressions for α_1 , α_2 , α_3 and α_4 produce $\mathcal{C}_{1-4} = 0$ in Eq. (104). At very high frequencies (above the 225th mode), positive exponential values cannot be represented by double precision floating-point arithmetic. To solve this issue, both the numerator and the denominator in the expressions of α_1 , α_2 and α_3 can be multiplied by $e^{-\lambda l}$. The resulting expression

for the mode shapes is given by:

$$u = \frac{\sin(\lambda l) - \cos(\lambda l) - e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - e^{-2\lambda l} + 2 e^{-\lambda l} \sin(\lambda l)} e^{\lambda(x-l)} + \frac{1 + (\sin(\lambda l) + \cos(\lambda l)) e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - e^{-2\lambda l} + 2 e^{-\lambda l} \sin(\lambda l)} e^{-\lambda x} + \frac{1 + e^{-2\lambda l} + 2 e^{-\lambda l} \cos(\lambda l)}{1 - e^{-2\lambda l} + 2 e^{-\lambda l} \sin(\lambda l)} \sin(\lambda x) - \cos(\lambda x). \quad (115)$$

Subsequently, Figure 4 shows the 1st and 15th mode shapes computed by the Lie symmetry approach (solid line) and the corresponding classical solution from Eq. (55) (dashed line). In this case, a beam of length $l = 1$ m having the following properties has been considered: cross-sectional area $S = 2.5 \times 10^{-4}$ m², Young's modulus $E = 70$ GPa, inertia moment $I = 5.2 \times 10^{-10}$ m⁴ and density $\rho = 2.7 \times 10^3$ kg/m³. In Figure 4, it is shown that the proposed approach is able to describe the mode shapes of the beam without round-off errors, even at high frequencies (contrary to the classical approach).

Figure 4: 1st and 15th mode shapes of a uniform clamped-free beam computed via the Lie symmetry approach (blue solid line) and the classical approach (black dashed line)

4.2.3 Example 2: mode shapes of a uniform sliding-free beam with a rotational spring and a concentrated mass

This second example consists in a more complex case of an Euler-Bernoulli beam with a left-sliding end ($x = 0$) and a right end ($x = l$) which is attached to a concentrated mass $m_2 = 1$ kg and a rotational spring of stiffness $K_{2,R} = 10^3$ N.m, represented in Figure 5. The properties of the beam are similar to those reported in the previous example. In this case, the BCs require that $u^{(1)}|_{x=0} = u^{(3)}|_{x=0} = 0$, $u^{(2)}|_{x=l} + K_{2,R} u^{(1)}|_{x=l} = 0$ and $u^{(3)}|_{x=l} - (EI/\rho S) m_2 \lambda^4 u|_{x=l} = 0$ (see Table 2). This gives the following restriction equations in accordance with Table 6:

Figure 5: Sketch of a uniform sliding beam with a rotational spring and a concentrated mass

$$-\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 - \alpha_3 = 0, \quad (116)$$

$$\alpha_1 - \alpha_2 - \alpha_3 = 0, \quad (117)$$

$$\alpha_1 \left(\lambda + \frac{K_{2,R}}{EI} \right) e^{\lambda l} + \alpha_2 \left(\lambda - \frac{K_{2,R}}{EI} \right) e^{-\lambda l} - \left(\alpha_3 \lambda + \alpha_4 \frac{K_{2,R}}{EI} \right) \sin(\lambda l) - \left(\alpha_4 \lambda - \alpha_3 \frac{K_{2,R}}{EI} \right) \cos(\lambda l) = 0, \quad (118)$$

$$\alpha_1 \left(1 + \frac{m_2}{\rho A} \lambda \right) e^{\lambda l} - \alpha_2 \left(1 - \frac{m_2}{\rho A} \lambda \right) e^{-\lambda l} + \left(\alpha_4 + \alpha_3 \frac{m_2}{\rho A} \lambda \right) \sin(\lambda l) - \left(\alpha_3 - \alpha_4 \frac{m_2}{\rho A} \lambda \right) \cos(\lambda l) = 0. \quad (119)$$

Then, the related frequency equation can be obtained from Appendix I:

$$e^{-\lambda l} \det \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & -1 & -1 & 0 \\ \left(\lambda + \frac{K_{2,R}}{EI} \right) e^{\lambda l} & \left(\lambda - \frac{K_{2,R}}{EI} \right) e^{-\lambda l} & -\lambda \sin(\lambda l) + \frac{K_{2,R}}{EI} \cos(\lambda l) & -\frac{K_{2,R}}{EI} \sin(\lambda l) - \lambda \cos(\lambda l) \\ \left(1 + \frac{m_2}{\rho A} \lambda \right) e^{\lambda l} & -\left(1 - \frac{m_2}{\rho A} \lambda \right) e^{-\lambda l} & \frac{m_2}{\rho A} \lambda \sin(\lambda l) - \cos(\lambda l) & \sin(\lambda l) + \frac{m_2}{\rho A} \lambda \cos(\lambda l) \end{bmatrix} = 0.$$

The mode shape expression with $\alpha_4 = 1$ follows as:

$$u = -\frac{\left(\sin(\lambda l) + \frac{m_2}{\rho A} \lambda \cos(\lambda l) \right) e^{\lambda(x-l)}}{\left(1 - \frac{m_2}{\rho A} \lambda \right) e^{-2\lambda l} - 1 - \frac{m_2}{\rho A} \lambda} - \frac{\left(\sin(\lambda l) + \frac{m_2}{\rho A} \lambda \cos(\lambda l) \right) e^{-\lambda(x+l)}}{\left(1 - \frac{m_2}{\rho A} \lambda \right) e^{-2\lambda l} - 1 - \frac{m_2}{\rho A} \lambda} - \cos(\lambda x). \quad (120)$$

Figure 6 shows the 1st ($\lambda_1 l = 2.4889662$) and 15th ($\lambda_{15} l = 45.790124$) mode shapes of the beam computed via the proposed approach. Again, one can notice that the numerical assessment of these mode shape curves is not prone to numerical issues at high frequencies.

Figure 6: 1st and 15th mode shapes of a uniform sliding-free beam with a rotational spring and a concentrated mass, computed via the Lie symmetry approach

4.2.4 Mode shape expressions for beams with classical and non-classical boundary conditions

An overview of several classical and non-classical BCs, including those already analyzed in the two preceding examples, is brought. Accordingly, Table 7 presents the parameters $\alpha_1 e^{\lambda x}$, $\alpha_2 e^{-\lambda x}$, $\alpha_3 \sin(\lambda x)$ and $\alpha_4 \cos(\lambda x)$ which appear in the expressions of the mode shapes of a beam subject to various kinds of classical BCs. Also, Table 8 gives the mode shapes of a beam subject to general boundary impedance terms, including added masses and springs. The related frequency equations for these classical and non-classical BCs are given in Appendix I. Also, Appendix I introduces the procedure for analyzing classical BCs from non-classical ones.

Table 7: Mode shapes of uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams with classical BCs

	$\alpha_1 e^{\lambda x}$	$\alpha_2 e^{-\lambda x}$	$\alpha_3 \sin(\lambda x)$	$\alpha_4 \cos(\lambda x)$	λl
clamped-clamped					
	$\frac{sc^- + e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^+} e^{\lambda(x-l)}$	$-\frac{1 - sc^+ e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^+} e^{-\lambda x}$	$-\frac{1 + ec^-}{1 - es^+} \sin(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$	$\lambda_1 l = 4.7300407$ $\lambda_2 l = 7.8532046$ $\lambda_3 l = 10.9956078$ $\lambda_4 l = 14.1371655$
free-free					
	$-\frac{sc^- + e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^+} e^{\lambda(x-l)}$	$\frac{1 - sc^+ e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^+} e^{-\lambda x}$	$-\frac{1 + ec^-}{1 - es^+} \sin(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$	$\lambda_5 l = 17.2787596$ $\lambda_n l \approx (2n+1)\frac{\pi}{2}, n > 5$
clamped-pinned					
	$\frac{sc^- + e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^+} e^{\lambda(x-l)}$	$-\frac{1 - sc^+ e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^+} e^{-\lambda x}$	$-\frac{1 + ec^-}{1 - es^+} \sin(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$	$\lambda_1 l = 3.9266023$ $\lambda_2 l = 7.0685827$ $\lambda_3 l = 10.2101761$ $\lambda_4 l = 13.3517688$
free-pinned					
	$\frac{sc^- - e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^+} e^{\lambda(x-l)}$	$\frac{1 + sc^+ e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^+} e^{-\lambda x}$	$-\frac{1 + ec^+}{1 - es^+} \sin(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$	$\lambda_5 l = 16.4933614$ $\lambda_n l \approx (4n+1)\frac{\pi}{4}, n > 5$
clamped-sliding					
	$\frac{sc^+ - e^{-\lambda l}}{1 + ec^-} e^{\lambda(x-l)}$	$-\frac{1 + sc^- e^{-\lambda l}}{1 + ec^-} e^{-\lambda x}$	$-\frac{1 - es^-}{1 + ec^-} \sin(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$	$\lambda_1 l = 2.3650204$ $\lambda_2 l = 5.497804$ $\lambda_3 l = 8.6393798$ $\lambda_4 l = 11.7809724$
free-sliding					
	$\frac{sc^+ + e^{-\lambda l}}{1 + ec^-} e^{\lambda(x-l)}$	$\frac{1 - sc^- e^{-\lambda l}}{1 + ec^-} e^{-\lambda x}$	$-\frac{1 - es^+}{1 + ec^-} \sin(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$	$\lambda_5 l = 14.9225651$ $\lambda_n l \approx (4n-1)\frac{\pi}{4}, n > 5$
clamped-free					
	$-\frac{sc^- - e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^+} e^{\lambda(x-l)}$	$-\frac{1 + sc^+ e^{-\lambda l}}{1 - es^+} e^{-\lambda x}$	$-\frac{1 + ec^+}{1 - es^+} \sin(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$	$\lambda_1 l = 1.8751041$ $\lambda_2 l = 4.6940911$ $\lambda_3 l = 7.8547574$ $\lambda_4 l = 10.9955407$ $\lambda_5 l = 14.1371684$ $\lambda_n l \approx (2n-1)\frac{\pi}{2}, n > 5$

$$sc^+ = \sin(\lambda l) + \cos(\lambda l), \quad es^+ = (e^{-\lambda l} + 2 \sin(\lambda l)) e^{-\lambda l}, \quad ec^+ = (e^{-\lambda l} + 2 \cos(\lambda l)) e^{-\lambda l},$$

$$sc^- = \sin(\lambda l) - \cos(\lambda l), \quad es^- = (e^{-\lambda l} - 2 \sin(\lambda l)) e^{-\lambda l}, \quad ec^- = (e^{-\lambda l} - 2 \cos(\lambda l)) e^{-\lambda l}.$$

Source: Prepared by the author.

Table 8: Mode shapes of uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams with non-classical BCs

	general non-classical boundaries
$\alpha_1 e^{\lambda x}$	$\left\{ \left(\lambda + \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 + \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) e^{-\lambda l} + \left[-EI \lambda^5 + (2\mathcal{M}_1 + \mathcal{M}_2) \lambda^4 + \frac{\mathcal{M}_1 + 2\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \nu_1 \lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1 \mathcal{M}_2}{(EI)^2} \nu_1 \right] \cos(\lambda l) \right.$ $\left. + \left[EI \lambda^5 + (\mathcal{M}_2 \lambda^2 + 2\nu_1) \lambda^2 - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} (2\mathcal{M}_2 \lambda^2 + \nu_1) \lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1 \mathcal{M}_2}{(EI)^2} \nu_1 \right] \sin(\lambda l) \right\} \frac{e^{\lambda(x-l)}}{\alpha_0}$
$\alpha_2 e^{-\lambda x}$	$\left\{ - \left(\lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 + \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) + \left[EI \lambda^5 + (2\mathcal{M}_1 + \mathcal{M}_2) \lambda^4 - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1 + 2\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \nu_1 \lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1 \mathcal{M}_2}{(EI)^2} \nu_1 \right] e^{-\lambda l} \cos(\lambda l) \right.$ $\left. + \left[EI \lambda^5 - (\mathcal{M}_2 \lambda^2 + 2\nu_1) \lambda^2 - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} (2\mathcal{M}_2 \lambda^2 + \nu_1) \lambda + \frac{\mathcal{M}_1 \mathcal{M}_2}{(EI)^2} \nu_1 \right] e^{-\lambda l} \sin(\lambda l) \right\} \frac{e^{-\lambda x}}{\alpha_0}$
$\alpha_3 \sin(\lambda x)$	$\left[\left(\lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 + 2\nu_1 \lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) + \left(\lambda + \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 - 2\nu_1 \lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) e^{-2kl} \right.$ $\left. - 2 \left(\lambda \cos(\lambda l) - \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \sin(\lambda l) \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 + \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) e^{-\lambda l} \right] \frac{\sin(\lambda x)}{\alpha_0}$
$\alpha_4 \cos(\lambda x)$	$\cos(\lambda x)$
α_0	$\left[- \left(\lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 - 2\mathcal{M}_1 \lambda^3 - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) + \left(\lambda + \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 + 2\mathcal{M}_1 \lambda^3 - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) e^{-2kl} \right.$ $\left. + 2 \left(\lambda \sin(\lambda l) + \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \cos(\lambda l) \right) \left(EI \lambda^4 + \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} \nu_1 \right) e^{-\lambda l} \right]$

Source: Prepared by the author.

4.3 MODE SHAPES OF UNIFORM TIMOSHENKO BEAMS

In the case of the mode shape equations of Timoshenko beams, Eqs. (59) and (60) admit the following prolonged infinitesimal generator in accordance with Eq. (16) for the space of variables $(x, u, \phi, u^{(1)}, \phi^{(1)}, u^{(2)}, \phi^{(2)})$:

$${}_{(2)}\mathcal{X} = \xi \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \eta_u \frac{\partial}{\partial u} + \eta_\phi \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi} + {}_{(1)}\eta_u \frac{\partial}{\partial u^{(1)}} + {}_{(1)}\eta_\phi \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi^{(1)}} + {}_{(2)}\eta_u \frac{\partial}{\partial u^{(2)}} + {}_{(2)}\eta_\phi \frac{\partial}{\partial \phi^{(2)}}, \quad (121)$$

where $\xi = \xi(x, u, \phi)$, $\eta_u = \eta_u(x, u, \phi)$ and $\eta_\phi = \eta_\phi(x, u, \phi)$ are the non-prolonged infinitesimal functions for point transformations and their prolongations follow from Eqs. (12) and (14). The infinitesimal criterion for invariance, from Eq. (18), provides the system of determining equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^4 \eta_u}{\partial x^4} + \frac{\lambda^2}{\beta} \left[(\beta + 1) \frac{\partial^2 \eta_u}{\partial x^2} + (\gamma - \lambda^2) \left(u \frac{\partial \eta_u}{\partial u} - \eta_u \right) \right] &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial^3 \eta_u}{\partial x^3} + \frac{\gamma - \lambda^2}{\beta} \left(\phi \frac{\partial \eta_u}{\partial u} - \eta_\phi \right) + \frac{\beta \lambda^2 + \gamma}{\beta} \frac{\partial \eta_u}{\partial x} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial^2 \eta_u}{\partial u^2} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial^2 \eta_u}{\partial x \partial u} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial \eta_u}{\partial \phi} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial \phi} &= 0, \\ \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial u} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \xi}{\partial x} &= 0, \end{aligned} \quad (122)$$

whose six independent solutions are listed in Table 9 in terms of the constant values c_1 , c_2 , c_3 , c_4 and c_5 of Eqs. (123 - 127).

Table 9: Lie point symmetries of the mode shape equation of uniform Timoshenko beams

\mathcal{X}_i	$\xi_{(i)}$	$\eta_{u(i)}$	$\eta_{\phi(i)}$
\mathcal{X}_1	1	0	0
\mathcal{X}_2	0	u	ϕ
\mathcal{X}_3	0	$e^{c_1 x}$	$c_1 c_3 e^{c_1 x}$
\mathcal{X}_4	0	$e^{-c_1 x}$	$-c_1 c_3 e^{-c_1 x}$
\mathcal{X}_5	0	$e^{c_2 x}$	$c_2 c_4 e^{c_2 x}$
\mathcal{X}_6	0	$e^{-c_2 x}$	$-c_2 c_4 e^{-c_2 x}$

Source: Prepared by the author.

$$c_1 = \sqrt{-\frac{\lambda^2 (\beta + 1) + c_5}{2\beta}}, \quad (123)$$

$$c_2 = \sqrt{-\frac{\lambda^2(\beta+1) - c_5}{2\beta}}, \quad (124)$$

$$c_3 = \frac{\lambda^2(\beta-1) + 2\gamma - c_5}{2(\gamma - \lambda^2)}, \quad (125)$$

$$c_4 = \frac{\lambda^2(\beta-1) + 2\gamma + c_5}{2(\gamma - \lambda^2)}, \quad (126)$$

$$c_5 = \lambda\sqrt{\lambda^2(\beta-1)^2 + 4\beta\gamma}. \quad (127)$$

Commutator tables can present Lie algebras concisely (OLVER, 1986; BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002). It shows all the commutator operations between the admitted symmetries, i.e., the infinitesimal generators from Table 9 in this case, where the table elements are $[\mathcal{X}_i, \mathcal{X}_j]$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, 6$ lines and $j = 1, 2, \dots, 6$ columns. In regard to this, Table 10 provides the commutator table for the Lie symmetries of the mode shape equations of uniform Timoshenko beams.

Table 10: Commutator table for the Lie point symmetries of the mode shape equations of uniform Timoshenko beams

	\mathcal{X}_1	\mathcal{X}_2	\mathcal{X}_3	\mathcal{X}_4	\mathcal{X}_5	\mathcal{X}_6
\mathcal{X}_1	0	0	$c_1\mathcal{X}_3$	$-c_1\mathcal{X}_4$	$c_2\mathcal{X}_5$	$-c_2\mathcal{X}_6$
\mathcal{X}_2	0	0	$-\mathcal{X}_3$	$-\mathcal{X}_4$	$-\mathcal{X}_5$	$-\mathcal{X}_6$
\mathcal{X}_3	$-c_1\mathcal{X}_3$	\mathcal{X}_3	0	0	0	0
\mathcal{X}_4	$c_1\mathcal{X}_4$	\mathcal{X}_4	0	0	0	0
\mathcal{X}_5	$-c_2\mathcal{X}_5$	\mathcal{X}_5	0	0	0	0
\mathcal{X}_6	$c_2\mathcal{X}_6$	\mathcal{X}_6	0	0	0	0

Source: Prepared by the author.

The infinitesimal generators \mathcal{X}_1 and \mathcal{X}_2 from Table 9 commute, i.e., $[\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_2] = 0$, and form an Abelian subalgebra. Once every Abelian subalgebra is solvable, this means that two symmetry reductions can be performed by these infinitesimal generators with no preferential ordering for that (HUMPHREYS, 1972). By taking \mathcal{X}_2 firstly, one can write the invariance relations:

$$\mathcal{X}_2\left\{r^1(x, u, \phi)\right\} = 0, \quad (1)\mathcal{X}_2\left\{v^1(x, u, \phi, u^{(1)}, \phi^{(1)})\right\} = 0, \quad (1)\mathcal{X}_2\left\{\psi^1(x, u, \phi, u^{(1)}, \phi^{(1)})\right\} = 0, \quad (128)$$

and

$$({}^k)\mathcal{X}_2\left\{v^{1(k-1)}(x, u, \phi, u^{(1)}, \phi^{(1)}, \dots, u^{(k)}, \phi^{(k)})\right\} = 0, \quad (129)$$

$${}_{(k)}\mathcal{X}_2 \left\{ \psi^{1^{(k-1)}}(x, u, \phi, u^{(1)}, \phi^{(1)}, \dots, u^{(k)}, \phi^{(k)}) \right\} = 0 \quad (k = 2, 3), \quad (130)$$

for the invariants of order lower than three. The resolution of these invariance relations refers to Section 2.5 of Chapter 2. Thus, this yields the following set of invariants:

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} \overset{1}{r} &= x, \overset{1}{v} = \frac{\phi}{u}, \overset{1}{\psi} = \frac{u^{(1)}}{u}, \overset{1}{v}^{(1)} = \frac{1}{u} \left(\phi^{(1)} - \frac{\phi u^{(1)}}{u} \right), \overset{1}{\psi}^{(1)} = \frac{1}{u} \left[u^{(2)} - \frac{(u^{(1)})^2}{u} \right], \\ \overset{1}{v}^{(2)} &= \frac{1}{u} \left[\phi^{(2)} - \frac{1}{u} (u^{(2)}\phi + 2 u^{(1)}\phi^{(1)}) + 2 \frac{(u^{(1)})^2 \phi}{u^2} \right] \end{aligned} \right\}. \quad (131)$$

Notice that $\overset{1}{\psi}^{(2)}$ is not presented in the set of invariants of Eq. (131), although it is admitted by Eq. (130). From the Differential Invariant Method, a single symmetry reduction for a system of ODEs (where at least one equation is of order higher than one) provides an order reduction in a single DE of the system (OLVER, 1986). It was chosen to perform this reduction of order for $u^{(2)}$ through the variable $\overset{1}{\psi}^{(1)}$, an explicit function of it ($\overset{1}{\psi}^{(2)}$ depend on $u^{(3)}$, which is not necessary for the space of variables of Eqs. (59) and (60)). Then, the two second-order mode shape equations of a Timoshenko beam can be transformed into one single order and one second order ODEs in the space of variable of the invariants from Eq. (131). Instead of writing these equations, a successive reduction of order is proposed by means of \mathcal{X}_1 , written for the new space of variables as follows:

$$\mathcal{X}_1 = \frac{\partial}{\partial \overset{1}{r}} \quad (132)$$

whose three first prolonged generators are equal to Eq. (132). The invariance relations for this infinitesimal generator in Eqs. (34) and (35) are given in the form:

$${}_{(1)}\mathcal{X}_1 \left\{ \overset{2}{r} \left(\overset{1}{r}, \overset{1}{v}, \overset{1}{\psi} \right) \right\} = 0, \quad {}_{(2)}\mathcal{X}_1 \left\{ \overset{2}{v} \left(\overset{1}{r}, \overset{1}{v}, \overset{1}{\psi}, \overset{1}{v}^{(1)}, \overset{1}{\psi}^{(1)} \right) \right\} = 0, \quad {}_{(2)}\mathcal{X}_1 \left\{ \overset{2}{\psi} \left(\overset{1}{r}, \overset{1}{v}, \overset{1}{\psi}, \overset{1}{v}^{(1)}, \overset{1}{\psi}^{(1)} \right) \right\} = 0, \quad (133)$$

and

$${}_{(3)}\mathcal{X}_1 \left\{ \overset{2(1)}{v} \left(\overset{1}{r}, \overset{1}{v}, \overset{1}{\psi}, \overset{1(1)}{v}, \overset{1(1)}{\psi}, \overset{1(2)}{v}, \overset{1(2)}{\psi} \right) \right\} = 0, \quad (134)$$

$${}_{(3)}\mathcal{X}_1 \left\{ \overset{2(1)}{\psi} \left(\overset{1}{r}, \overset{1}{v}, \overset{1}{\psi}, \overset{1(1)}{v}, \overset{1(1)}{\psi}, \overset{1(2)}{v}, \overset{1(2)}{\psi} \right) \right\} = 0. \quad (135)$$

From these relations it follows the set of invariants:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \overset{2}{r} = \overset{1}{v}, \overset{2}{v} = \overset{1}{\phi}, \overset{2}{\psi} = \overset{1(1)}{v}, \overset{2(1)}{v} = \frac{\overset{1(1)}{\psi}}{\overset{1(1)}{v}}, \overset{2(1)}{\psi} = \frac{\overset{1(2)}{v}}{\overset{1(1)}{v}} \end{array} \right\} \quad (136)$$

which configures the new space of variables $\left(\overset{2}{r}, \overset{2}{v}, \overset{2}{\psi}, \overset{2(1)}{v}, \overset{2(1)}{\psi} \right)$ for the Timoshenko mode shape equations. By a change of variables¹⁸ with the invariants from Eq. (136) in the aforementioned equations, the two first order ODEs are obtained:

$$\overset{2(1)}{v} + \frac{\overset{2}{v}(\overset{2}{v} - \overset{2}{r}) + \lambda^2}{\overset{2}{\psi}} - 1 = 0, \quad (137)$$

and

$$\overset{2(1)}{\psi} + \frac{\overset{2}{v}(\beta \overset{2}{r} + \gamma) - \overset{2}{r}(\lambda^2(\beta - 1) + \gamma)}{\beta \overset{2}{\psi}} + 2 \overset{2}{v} + \overset{2}{r} = 0. \quad (138)$$

where $\overset{2}{v} = \overset{2}{v}(\overset{2}{r})$ and $\overset{2}{\psi} = \overset{2}{\psi}(\overset{2}{r})$.

An additional reduction of an order may be performed in Eqs. (137) and (138) if it admits any remaining symmetry from Table 9, which can be checked computing the ideal subalgebras in the case of existing a solvable Lie algebra. For this, the symmetry reductions must obey the structure of the chain of subalgebras in the form of Eq. (1). The motivation for additional reductions is related to the possibility of reducing the system of two first-order equations to a single ODE.

The resolution of the system of reduced-order equations from Eqs. (137) and (138) yields the closed-form solutions of mode shapes of Timoshenko beams, Eqs. (61), (64), and (65), such as in the literature. Here, the advantage of having first-order ODEs instead of the original ones falls on the point that the reduced equations are tougher to solve via symbolic methods. Although symmetry reductions from the set $\{\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_2\}$ result in the adversity as mentioned above, other infinitesimal generators can be taken from Table 9 and, under the chain of subalgebras, employed to get new reduced mode shape equations.

¹⁸Notice that a direct change of variables can be done for a double order reduction by relating the physical variables from $(x, u, \phi, u^{(1)}, \phi^{(1)}, u^{(2)}, \phi^{(2)})$ to the $\left(\overset{2}{r}, \overset{2}{v}, \overset{2}{\psi}, \overset{2(1)}{v}, \overset{2(1)}{\psi} \right)$ -space.

4.4 PARTIAL REMARKS

The mode shape equation of rods with varying cross-sections converts into a Riccati equation helped by the variable's space spanned by the differential invariants and its admitted Lie symmetries. In addition, the development of a complementary approach for converting this Riccati equation into quadratures with the help of canonical coordinates eases the solution procedure. Within this framework, the Lie symmetry method validates its proposition of keeping solutions invariant for reduced-order ODEs, illustrated by examples of rods with specific cross-section areas. These admitted order reductions yield the possibility of dealing with BVPs set up on reduced spaces of variables, e.g., the $(r, v, v^{(1)})$ -space of Eq. (73) (or even given by the canonical coordinates), if its BCs also admit the referring Lie group. Numerical methods for solving DEs may be used in this context for the reduced BVP in addition to symbolic solution methods.

An invariance formulation through the Lie symmetries of BVPs for vibrating uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams provides new expressions for their mode shapes. These mode shapes are written as functions of symmetry transformation parameters, which do not exhibit instabilities when numerically assessed at high frequencies. This approach circumvents inaccurate numerical evaluations of solutions that are highly sensitive to round-off errors, such as the displacement solution of Eq. (55). Therefore, it produces exact mode shape solutions described for several boundary configurations, including classical and non-classical BCs.

The Lie symmetry analysis of the Timoshenko beam mode shape equations gives order reductions for these equations by taking the invariant differentials associated with the symmetries of the problem. An admitted two-dimensional subalgebra provides the reduction of the original system of ODEs to two first-order ODEs. Although detailed for the simplest two-dimensional subalgebra, it is worth mentioning that the procedure for order reductions can be considered for all infinitesimal generators of Table 9. However, successive reductions may not be carried out for every one of these transformations. This remark suggests the necessity of computing the chain of ideal subalgebras once the number of admitted reductions is directly related to the dimension of the solvable Lie algebra of the problem. Another point in consideration is the possibility of dealing with BVPs of Timoshenko beams in a new space of variables, similarly to the study presented for rods with varying cross-section areas and Euler-Bernoulli beams.

5 FINAL REMARKS

This chapter summarizes the conclusions of this partial report. In addition, it outlines potential next steps for this research, including the topic of computing exact solutions for mode shapes of vibrating plates.

5.1 PARTIAL CONCLUSIONS

The study of Lie symmetries of DEs and BVPs of mechanical vibrating systems reveals interesting transformations for providing reduced-order equations in new spaces of variables. In practice, the assessment of symmetries by the Lie symmetry method can turn into numerous and cumbersome calculations. Besides that, modern computer algebra succeeds in accomplishing results for them efficiently due to the highly algorithmic method's nature. Meanwhile, when it comes to the computation of mode shapes of vibrating structures such as rods and beams, the consideration of non-uniform elements can preclude the achievement of symbolic solutions by traditional methods in some cases, and Lie symmetries are helpful on that. Even problems whose closed-form solutions are already available, interesting viewpoints can be provided by symmetries. This research presented the Lie symmetry method followed by a review on vibration models of rods and beams, focusing on mode shape solutions to study these vibration problems via the Lie symmetry method.

For the longitudinal vibration of non-uniform rods with varying cross-section areas, the Lie symmetries admitted by its mode shape equation yield a Riccati equation by an order reduction through the associated differential invariants from the new space of variables. It is worth mentioning that a further study of the above-mentioned first-order equation can be carried out, e.g., seeking closed-form solutions of Riccati-type equations for arbitrary cross-sectional area function or exploring alternative symmetries¹⁹ for additional transformations. On the other hand, the specification of the cross-sectional area function spawn new Lie point symmetries and, in the case of admitting a two-dimensional solvable Lie algebra, this allows converting the referring Riccati equation into a quadrature. This

¹⁹Besides the addressed Lie (point) symmetries in this work, several kinds of mathematical symmetries such as Lie-Bäcklund, variational, nonlocal, and hidden symmetries can be explored for vibrating problems (CANTWELL, 2002).

may represent an easier integration and resolution of equations that can provide mode shape functions of structures. Additionally, the invariance formulation for BVPs yields reduced-order BVPs by mapping BCs of the problem into new ones for the reduced space of variables.

Although analytical solutions for mode shapes of uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams are well-known in literature, their numerical assessment is usually prone to ill-conditioning at high frequencies. Among the techniques for avoiding inaccurate values at the numerical evaluation of these mode shapes, a suitable space accomplishes expressions for given BVPs for beams that do not become inaccurate, found by the Lie symmetry analysis. Thus, exact mode shape functions were provided through the invariance formulation for Euler-Bernoulli beam BVPs, circumventing the round-off errors at high frequencies. These mode shape expressions were presented in tables for several classical and non-classical boundary configurations to ease these results application. Thus, the Lie symmetry approach can be set aside when only using these results from the prepared tables.

Once the motivation for studying the Timoshenko beam vibrating model arose from the possibility of turning it into a more compact domain by the Lie symmetry method, the complete invariance of BVPs was analyzed to reach a simpler beam model without adding further simplifications to the modeling. The achievement of this result represents an easier way to assess the vibration behavior of Timoshenko beams. Additionally to the simpler computation of closed-form solutions, new reduced BVPs may reveal benefits in terms of computational demand. Notwithstanding that only the model's differential equations have been reduced, a further study has to be performed about the invariance of BCs for a given beam to reach this "compact model".

5.2 NEXT STEPS

Suggestions of the next steps for this research are given as follows:

1. Evaluate different cross-sectional area functions of non-uniform vibrating rods either by the resolution of the reduced-order Riccati equation or using canonical coordinates. In the latter, the conversion of the reduced equation into quadratures requires additional Lie symmetries to provide closed-form solutions for the mode shapes.
2. Expand the study on the invariance formulation for BVPs of vibrating rods with varying cross-sectional areas. From this, potential reduced-order BVPs can be found, and, if convenient, numerical methods applied for assisting the resolution of the re-

duced DEs. The analysis of nonlinear BCs can also be carried out, for instance, considering nonlinear springs with cubic stiffness. At this point, it should be highlighted that Lie point transformations may provide linearizations techniques, suggesting the possibility of dealing with reduced-order linear BVPs in the case of nonlinear BCs (AL-DWEIK *et al.*, 2015; QADIR, 2012).

3. Develop a study about mode shapes of non-uniform Euler-Bernoulli beams similarly to the presented approach for rods. This study may yield reduced-order equations from which one can assess mode shapes for the general and specific cross-sectional areas and moment of inertia functions, accordingly to complete invariance of the admitted BCs. Preliminary results suggest an equivalent symmetry arrangement to the case of non-uniform rods, i.e., one explicit symmetry transformation and the remaining ones written as functions of beam parameters such as the cross-sectional area function and moment of inertia.
4. Compute the chain of subalgebras from the Lie algebra of the mode shape equations of Timoshenko beams, providing a complete understanding of the possible reductions of order admitted by these equations. Then, if these equations admit at least a three-dimensional solvable Lie algebra, the two second-order ODEs could be mapped to a single ODE by three successive reductions of order. Additionally, if a BVP holds the same subgroup of transformations applied to the order reduction procedure, it can be converted to a reduced-order one, possibly simplifying the problem solution. The best-case scenario relies on the existence of a subgroup simultaneously admitted by several BCs. For this, one could write transformed BCs for reduced equations systematically. The BCs could be disposed of in tables for a unique reduced equation or set of equations.
5. Depending on the results of the aforementioned non-uniform structures, vibration modes of non-uniform Timoshenko beams, i.e., natural frequencies and mode shapes, should be considered under the Lie symmetry view.
6. Study the mode shape equation of rectangular plates, better discussed in the following.

5.2.1 Mode shapes of rectangular plates

Warburton (1954) derived approximate mode shape solutions of rectangular plates as products of mode shapes of Euler-Bernoulli beams. The combination of the classical BCs

clamped, free, and pinned yields 21 different configurations for plates. Exact solutions are known for six of them (VOIGT, 1893; ZEISSIG, 1898). Leissa (1973) provided more accurate formulas than in Warburton (1954)'s work, although they were still approximate expressions based on the Rayleigh-Ritz method. In general, these non-exact approaches provide frequencies higher than the actual value. To the author's knowledge, no similar use of the Lie symmetries is found in the literature for studying mode shapes of rectangular plates. A short description of the vibrating model of rectangular plates is presented in the following as well as some considerations on the Lie symmetry method for the problem.

Assuming the displacement function $\tilde{w} = \tilde{w}(x, y, t)$ for a transversely vibrating rectangular plate, where $x \in [x_1, x_2]$ and $y \in [y_1, y_2]$ are the spatial coordinates of the plate and $t \geq 0$ is the time, harmonic solutions $\tilde{w} = w e^{i\omega t}$ can be assumed in order to eliminate time dependency and provide the following mode shape equation (LOVE, 2013; LEISSA, 1973):

$$\frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial x^4} + \frac{\partial^4 w}{\partial y^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} - \lambda^4 w = 0, \quad x \in]x_1, x_2[, y \in]y_1, y_2[, \quad (139)$$

where $w = w(x, y)$ and $\lambda = (\rho\omega^2/D)^{\frac{1}{4}}$ is the wavenumber, $D = Eh^3/[12(1 - \nu^2)]$ being the plate's flexural stiffness, E is the Young's modulus, ν is the Poisson's ration, h is the thickness and ρ is the density of the plate.

At this point, one should notice that the mode shape equation from Eq. (139) is a PDE and the Lie symmetry method described in Chapter 2 for ODEs does not fit exactly the current equation. However, suitable Lie symmetries for PDEs can be found by a slightly modification on the group of Eq. (2), i.e., by considering additional independent variables in such a way that the target space of variables for the point transformation becomes $(\bar{\mathbf{x}}, \bar{z})$ for a single PDE²⁰, where $\bar{\mathbf{x}} = X_i$ ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n_i$) for n_i independent variables. Back to the vibration problem, these point transformations map (x, y, w) into $(\bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{w})$ and the admitted infinitesimal functions are introduced as $\xi_x = \xi_x(x, y, w)$, $\xi_y = \xi_y(x, y, w)$ and $\eta = \eta(x, y, w)$. In the same way, the infinitesimal criterion for invariance is defined for the new space and, in summary, the solutions of the corresponding determining equations are found in Table 11.

Each Lie symmetry transformation provides a single reduction in the number of independent variables for PDEs. The resulting reduced equations only preserve the solution of the original PDE if the entire BVP (or IBVP) is also invariant under the same Lie group action that reduced the PDE (BLUMAN; ANCO, 2002). However, it is possible to recon-

²⁰For systems of PDEs, correspondingly, the $(\bar{\mathbf{x}}, \bar{z})$ -space of variables has to be considered, where $\bar{\mathbf{x}} = (\bar{x}_1, \bar{x}_2, \dots, \bar{x}_{n_i})$ and $\bar{z} = (\bar{z}_1, \bar{z}_2, \dots, \bar{z}_{n_d})$.

Table 11: Lie point symmetries of the mode shape equation of plates

\mathcal{X}_i	$\xi_{x(i)}$	$\xi_{y(i)}$	$\eta(i)$
\mathcal{X}_1	1	0	0
\mathcal{X}_2	0	1	0
\mathcal{X}_3	0	0	w
\mathcal{X}_4	y	$-x$	0
\mathcal{X}_5	0	0	$e^{\lambda x}$
\mathcal{X}_6	0	0	$e^{-\lambda x}$
\mathcal{X}_7	0	0	$e^{\lambda y}$
\mathcal{X}_8	0	0	$e^{-\lambda y}$
\mathcal{X}_9	0	0	$\sin(\lambda x)$
\mathcal{X}_{10}	0	0	$\cos(\lambda x)$
\mathcal{X}_{11}	0	0	$\sin(\lambda y)$
\mathcal{X}_{12}	0	0	$\cos(\lambda y)$

Source: Prepared by the author.

struct solutions for linear PDEs from the resolution of these reduced-space equations even if the BCs of the problem are not invariant under the Lie group. This procedure of computing solutions for PDEs by solutions of reduced equations is known as a superposition of invariant solutions (KUMAR; RANI, 2021; OLVER, 1986).

All twelve Lie symmetries from Table 11 are able to convert the PDE of Eq. (139) into ODEs by compressing the two independent variables into a single new coordinate. The non-repeated solutions of these twelve ODEs are given by Eqs. (140 - 144).

$$w_1 = \mathcal{C}_1 e^{\lambda x} + \mathcal{C}_2 e^{-\lambda x} + \mathcal{C}_3 \sin(\lambda x) + \mathcal{C}_4 \cos(\lambda x), \quad (140)$$

$$w_2 = \mathcal{C}_1 e^{\lambda y} + \mathcal{C}_2 e^{-\lambda y} + \mathcal{C}_3 \sin(\lambda y) + \mathcal{C}_4 \cos(\lambda y), \quad (141)$$

$$w_3 = \mathcal{C}_1 e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda x} + \mathcal{C}_2 e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda x} + \mathcal{C}_3 \sin\left(\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda x\right) + \mathcal{C}_4 \cos\left(\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda x\right), \quad (142)$$

$$w_4 = \mathcal{C}_1 e^{\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda y} + \mathcal{C}_2 e^{-\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda y} + \mathcal{C}_3 \sin\left(\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda y\right) + \mathcal{C}_4 \cos\left(\frac{\sqrt{2}}{2}\lambda y\right), \quad (143)$$

$$w_5 = \mathcal{C}_1 I_0\left(\lambda\sqrt{x^2+y^2}\right) + \mathcal{C}_2 J_0\left(\lambda\sqrt{x^2+y^2}\right) + \mathcal{C}_3 K_0\left(\lambda\sqrt{x^2+y^2}\right) + \mathcal{C}_4 Y_0\left(\lambda\sqrt{x^2+y^2}\right), \quad (144)$$

where \mathcal{C}_1 , \mathcal{C}_2 , \mathcal{C}_3 , and \mathcal{C}_4 are constants of integration, which follow from the BCs of the plate, J_0 and Y_0 are Bessel functions of the first and second kinds and I_0 and K_0 are

the modified Bessel functions of the first and second kinds, respectively, for the invariant solutions w_1 , w_2 , w_3 , w_4 and w_5 .

The vibrating solutions from Warburton (1954) are given in terms of mode shapes of beams, in the same way the first four presented invariant solutions²¹ for both directions x and y . This suggests that their superposition may be related to the available formulas in the literature for mode shapes of plates. Besides the physical interpretation of these four solutions, w_5 seems to be peculiar in this set of admitted invariant solutions and may be related a circular effect as suggested by the functions of $\sqrt{x^2+y^2}$. The restrictive use of vibration mode of beams to construct solutions for plates fails to accurately represent corner effects/conditions for free edges or corners. On this occasion, it is intended to study if w_5 encompass the aforementioned lacking behavior and, then, assemble the analytical solution for mode shapes of plates from the superposition of invariant solutions.

²¹Notice that the invariant solutions w_1 and w_3 as well as w_2 and w_4 are almost the same, or, at least, describe the same phenomenon. This may represent redundant solutions in the set of invariant solutions and, hence, that the symmetries of the problem are not “organized” in such a way that it may not occur. In order to get this, an optimal system of invariant solutions has to be computed from an optimal system of subalgebras, from where any admitted symmetry can be derived (OLVER, 1986; DEVI; YADAV; ARORA, 2021).

APPENDIX I

The following frequency equations have been obtained via the Lie symmetry method associated to the invariance formulation for BCs and then multiplied by $e^{-\lambda l}$ to obtain more stable equations at high frequencies (GONÇALVES; PEPLOW; BRENNAN, 2018).

A. Euler-Bernoulli beam of length l subject to some classical BCs.

(a) Clamped-clamped and free-free beams:

$$\cos(\lambda l)(1 + e^{-2\lambda l}) - 2e^{-\lambda l} = 0.$$

(b) Clamped-pinned and free-pinned beams:

$$(1 - e^{-2\lambda l}) \cos(\lambda l) - (1 + e^{-2\lambda l}) \sin(\lambda l) = 0.$$

(c) Clamped-sliding and free-sliding beams:

$$(1 - e^{-2\lambda l}) \cos(\lambda l) + (1 + e^{-2\lambda l}) \sin(\lambda l) = 0.$$

(d) Clamped-free beam:

$$\cos(\lambda l)(1 + e^{-2\lambda l}) + 2e^{-\lambda l} = 0.$$

B. Euler-Bernoulli beam of length l subject to general non-classical BCs.

$$e^{-\lambda l} \det(\mathbf{M}) = 0,$$

where

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda + \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} & \lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} & \frac{\mathcal{M}_1}{EI} & -\lambda \\ \lambda^3 - \frac{\mathcal{V}_1}{EI} & -\lambda^3 - \frac{\mathcal{V}_1}{EI} & -\lambda^3 & -\frac{\mathcal{V}_1}{EI} \\ \left(\lambda - \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI}\right) e^{\lambda l} & \left(\lambda + \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI}\right) e^{-\lambda l} & -\lambda \sin(\lambda l) - \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \cos(\lambda l) & \frac{\mathcal{M}_2}{EI} \sin(\lambda l) - \lambda \cos(\lambda l) \\ \left(\lambda^3 + \frac{\mathcal{V}_2}{EI}\right) e^{\lambda l} & -\left(\lambda^3 - \frac{\mathcal{V}_2}{EI}\right) e^{-\lambda l} & \frac{\mathcal{V}_2}{EI} \sin(\lambda l) - \lambda^3 \cos(\lambda l) & \lambda^3 \sin(\lambda l) + \frac{\mathcal{V}_2}{EI} \cos(\lambda l) \end{bmatrix}.$$

The characteristic equation given by $e^{-\lambda l} \det(\mathbf{M}) = 0$ is general and may be applied to retrieve some characteristic equations for beams with classical BCs or mixed classical

and non-classical BCs. For instance, for a clamped-clamped beam, one has $\mathcal{M}_i \rightarrow \infty$ and $\mathcal{V}_i \rightarrow \infty$ ($i = 1, 2$). In this case, the characteristic equation $e^{-\lambda l} \det(\mathbf{M}) = 0$ yields:

$$e^{-\lambda l} \det \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 1 & 0 \\ -1 & -1 & 0 & -1 \\ -e^{\lambda l} & e^{-\lambda l} & -\cos(\lambda l) & \sin(\lambda l) \\ e^{\lambda l} & e^{-\lambda l} & \sin(\lambda l) & \cos(\lambda l) \end{bmatrix} = 0,$$

which gives the frequency equation for a clamped-clamped beam, see case A.(a).

Additionally, $\mathcal{M}_i = 0$ and $\mathcal{V}_i \rightarrow \infty$ for a pinned boundary at $x = l_i$, $\mathcal{M}_i \rightarrow \infty$ and $\mathcal{V}_i = 0$ for a sliding boundary and $\mathcal{M}_i = 0$ and $\mathcal{V}_i = 0$ for a free boundary.

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